

Review Article

"G-D's Physics" Points at a Singular Higher "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR)!

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is affiliated with Zefat Academic Center (and has been affiliated with Ariel University), and is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in further direct validation of the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics; Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentovish@gmail.com

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This major Paradigmatic-Shift follows a preceding "Paradigmatic Crisis" of the Old MCR Paradigm, as signified by a fundamental "theoretical inconsistency" between its two primary "pillars", e.g., General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM), and its principle inability to account for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (i.e., assumed to be "explained" by the purely hypothetical concepts of "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" which failed to be detected even after two decades of intensive experimentation!?) Based on direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two unique "Critical Predictions" associated with "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" postulate's predicted "Non-Continuous Increase in the Universe's Expansion Rate" (UNCIARE) during the "Jewish Rosh-Hashana" (two days special time interval), and the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings – as more valid than corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, "G-D's Physics" is accepted as the New valid Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm! The key discovery made by "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm is that there exists a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass") for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!" thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) that comprise the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! The theoretical implications of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm are quite far reaching: it unifies (for the first time in Physics) between these Four basic Physical Features within a newly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which also integrates GRT & QM! Perhaps, most significant is "G-D's Physics" pointing at the singularity of this UCP (or "Universal Consciousness Reality", UCR) which solely exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, as well as solely exists (without the presence of the physical universe) "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s; and "steers" the universe towards the fulfilment of its "Ultimate Perfected Geualh Goal" in which Science (and Humanity) recognize this singularity of the UCP/UCR which is also characterized by "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony" (that is initiated with the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm)!

Introduction

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is currently undergoing a major "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" (previously termed: the "Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT)! This major Paradigmatic-Shift inevitably follows the fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the Old MCR Paradigm that was signified by:

- Theoretical Inconsistency in the Foundations of the "Old Standard Paradigm":** The appearance of certain "theoretical-inconsistencies" within the foundations of the "Old Standard Paradigm" signify a "'Paradigmatic-Crisis"!
- Key "Unexplained Empirical Phenomenon":** Another clear sign of the existence of a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the "Old Standard Paradigm" is the inability of this Old Paradigm to explain key empirical phenomenon!? According to Kuhn, following the appearance of such a "Paradigmatic-Cri-

sis" of the "Old Standard Paradigm" there must arise a discovery of a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) which must meet specific "stringent scientific criteria", including:

- Be able to explain (and replicate) all known phenomena (and laws) explained by the "Old Standard Paradigm" (OSP).
- Successfully resolve those "Theoretical-Inconsistencies" found in the foundation of the Old Standard Paradigm.
- Offer an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for that "Key Unresolved Empirical Phenomenon" (which the "Old Standard Paradigm" could not account for).
- Additionally, the (candidate) "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) must also identify at least one (unique) "Critical Prediction" that differentiates it from the corresponding prediction/s of the "Old Standard Paradigm" (OSP); and empirically validate this unique "Critical Prediction" of the NSP as "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of the OSP!

e) * An added value for this (candidate) NSP is to the extent that it is capable of offering a "broader theoretical framework" that will be shown capable of significantly advancing our understanding of this specific scientific discipline, i.e., such as a unification of apparently "distinct" phenomena, laws etc.

According to Kuhn's analysis it is sufficient for the (candidate) NSP to satisfy at least the first four (a-d) of these "stringent scientific criteria" in order to be accepted by the Scientific Community as the New Scientific Paradigm in this specific scientific discipline! Nevertheless, after satisfying those "first four" stringent scientific criteria, to the extent that the NSP is shown capable also satisfying the fifth condition ϵ , then this (undoubtedly) adds a significant "theoretical validity" this NSP, hence advancing (significantly) our understanding of the physical universe's behavior and characteristics (e.g., as seen from the "vantage point" of that specific scientific subdiscipline)!

Indeed, such was the case with Einstein's "monumental" discovery and empirical validation of "General Relativity Theory" (GRT) "NSP" for Twentieth Century Physics – as replacing the OSP of Newtonian Mechanics & Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory! Einstein's GRT was shown capable of:

- a) Resolving the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between Newtonian Classical Mechanics and Maxwellian Electromagnetic Theory.
- b) Discarding the purely hypothetical "Ether" concept, e.g., as "superfluous" (i.e., "non-existent") – which could not be "detected" by Newtonian Mechanics (despite numerous experimental attempts to do so!)
- c) Identifying at least one (unique) "Critical Prediction" that can differentiate the predictions of the "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) of GRT from the Old Scientific Paradigm of Newtonian Mechanics: i.e., regrading GRT's "double-valued curvature of Mercury's perihelion pathway around the Sun" (e.g. 1.6 ARC due to the Sun's mass' curvature of Space-Time), as opposed to Newton's only 0.8 ARC predicted value!?
- d) Empirical Validation of GRT's "double-valued Mercury's perihelion's pathway curvature" (around the Sun: 1.6 ARC, as opposed to Newton's only 0.8 ARC predicted value)!?
- e) * Compelling theoretical advancement of 20th Century's Theoretical Physics brought about by GRT's (unique) unification between "pairs" of the "Space-Time" (continuum), and "Energy-Mass" (equivalence), and the "curvature of Space-Time" by (certain) "massive objects" (which affects the "travelling-pathways" of these "massive" and other "less-massive" objects)!

In much the same manner, it is suggested in this (breakthrough seminal) scientific article that there exists a basic "Paradigmatic-Crisis" found within the very foundations of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm – signified by fundamental "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM (e.g., associated with GRT's "Speed of Light Barrier" as opposed to QM's empirically validated "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon indicating the apparent "instantaneous" transmission of signal across space and time?!); and the principle inability of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm to account for the accelerated expansion of the universe – i.e., assumed to be "explained" by purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" (which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe but yet could not be detected experimentally despite over two full decades of intensive experimental efforts to do so!?) Consequently, a New Scientific Paradigm termed: "G-D's Physics" (e.g., previously also called: the "Computational Unified Field Theory") has been discovered which is if validated empirically – based on the above list of "stringent scientific criteria" (a-e*) will lead to its unequivocal acceptance as the New satisfactory Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Indeed, one of the profound theoretical implications of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century Physics) is its unique capacity to completely unify between the Four (basic) Physical Features (e.g., of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass"), and in fact point at the singularity of a higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (at an "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec"),

thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! It therefore advances Physics basic understanding of the entire physical universe – not only in terms of fulfilling Einstein's (lifelong) Quest for a "Unifying Field Theory" that could completely unify between GRT & QM, but could also unify between those Four basic Physical Features (in one simple formula)! But also goes even beyond Einstein's ("historic") Quest to point at this singular UCP which is shown to comprise a "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which solely exists both "during" its extremely rapid computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! [1-47].

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(n)\}] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\}) / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i\dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value. "G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by Pohl et al. (2010):

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al. (2010) set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?! In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its abovementioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(n)\}] = O(i\dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i\dots n)\}) / h * n\{UF's(i\dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical). This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more

"spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements! Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" (Karr & Hilico, 2012), interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction, (Onofrio, 2013; Zyga, 2013), higher dimension gravity, (Dahia, & Lemos., 2016), a new boson, (McKeen & Miller, 2016) and the quasi-free hypothesis π^+ (Lestone, 2017); and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashanah" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar

Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Hence, to the extent that these two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm are empirically validated, then this will convince the Scientific Community that the New "G-D's Physics" has to be accepted as a satisfactory New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics! Based on such direct empirical validation of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a discussion ensues of the manner in which "G-D's Physics" newly discovered singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) is capable of computing every exhaustive spatial pixel or "object" (e.g., including "human-beings" as opposed to "non-human": "inanimate" material object/s, as well as "animate": plants and animals) – based on a further discovery of the UCP's "Gimateria" (i.e., Hebrew letters' numerical values) of each object's five "secondary-essential" "Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (HCD's) of: "Chessed", "Gevurah", "Tiferet", "Neztach" & "Hod" (e.g., each of them comprising "ten zero's" out of the "fifty zero's" comprising the incredible rate of the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe: $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)! As will be discussed, this entirely new conception of the manner in which this singular, higher-ordered UCP computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's "object" in the universe is "non-material", i.e., exemplifying the "translation" of the fundamental new "building-blocks" ("or "Atoms" – metaphorically) of the entire physical universe from the Hebrew letters' "Gimatria" (numerical values, also associated with these five "secondary-essential" HCD's corresponding "ten zero's") to the production of each ("human" or "non-human") object's unique physical characteristics! Indeed, it is shown that this novel manner in which the UCP is seen to compute the specific physical characteristics of each individual (unique "human" or "non-human") "object" is a part and parcel of the UCP's overall "Blueprint Plan" of steering the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" material composition through its "animate": "plants", "animals", human-beings – leading to the fulfillment of the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of a "Moral", "Spiritual" and even "Physical" "Perfected" state of the universe in which the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), e.g., characterized by "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" being recognized (and accepted) by Science and Humanity (more generally)!

Discussion

The Significance of the current empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two unique "Critical Predictions" – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT's and QM's is indeed profound and quite "far-reaching":

(and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) – is entirely dependent upon- and in fact is but a manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality"! Hence, whether we examine the universe at the "microscopic" quantum level or "macroscopic" relativistic level, we reach the inevitable conclusion that the universe does not operate based on any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between certain "massive-objects" and their (assumed) "causing" of the "curvature of Space-Time", or based on any (direct or indirect) physical relationships between any subatomic "target's" (assumed "probability wave-function") and corresponding "probe" element – which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of the target's "probability wave-function" (into a

singular "complimentary" energy-space or mass-time value)! Instead, "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's discovery of the existence of a singular higher, "Universal Consciousness Reality" – upon which the entire "existence", "dissolution", and "evolution" of the universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) entirely depends alters our basic understanding of the basic nature, dynamics and evolution of the universe; we realize that none of the multifarious "relativistic" or "quantum" elements, forces, or particles etc. exists "continuously" – but only "transiently" and "phenomenally" as a manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCR, which constitutes the only "real" continuous "reality" underlying the entire physical universe! There are two direct theoretical ramifications ensuing from this profound realization of the New (empirically validated) "G-d's Physics" discovery of the existence of this singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR): a). The UCR's "Universal Computational Formula": Negating the "Standard Model's" Material-Causal Assumption! First, this profound realization of "G-d's Physics" singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) constituting the only "real" reality underlying the "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the physical universe – when combined with "G-d's Physics" discovery of the singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe through the UCP's simultaneous integrated computation of the four basic physical features (of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time") for each exhaustive spatial pixel; reveals that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical relationship" between any "independent" material entities, e.g., be it relativistic "massive-objects"/"less-massive objects" and their assumed "curvature of Space-Time", or be it any subatomic particles, forces, entities etc.! This is simply because (once again) this UCP's singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – so there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, or between any two (or more) subatomic "particles", "forces" etc. This possesses profound theoretical ramifications – i.e., first and foremost, it negates the basic "Material-Causal" assumption underlying the "Standard Model"! This is because the basic "Material-Causal" assumption underlying the "Standard Model" is that it is based on direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain elementary particles and other particles that Three (out of four) Forces of Nature, i.e., "Weak"/"Strong" Nuclear Force", and "Electromagnetic Force" are being explained (e.g., with the fourth "Gravitational Force" currently not being explained by the "Standard Model"); But, since according to this "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), then there cannot exist any such "material-causal" direct (or even indirect) physical interactions between any two (or more) "elementary particles", "forces" etc.! Therefore, instead of the current "Standard Model", which explains those Three Forces in terms of them arising from an assumed direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between specific "particles" or "forces", the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm suggests that the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s), thereby giving rise to the entire UF's frame and negating the possibility of the existence of any direct or indirect "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such subatomic particles; Interestingly, this New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm has been shown to offer a satisfactory alternative explanation replicating all relativistic and quantum phenomena, laws, and effects based on the discovery of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR's consecutive computation of an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") Thus, for instance, the New "G-d's Physics" accounted for the apparent "curvature of Space-Time" by certain "massive-objects" alternatively through its conceptualization of the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) based on two (out of three) of its "Computational Dimen-

sions", i.e., of "Framework" ("frame"/"object") and "Consistency" ("consistent"/"inconsistent") giving rise to the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy" (e.g., "Frame"-consistent and "inconsistent" UCP's computation), "mass" and "time" (e.g., "Object"-consistent and "inconsistent" computational measures, respectively); Indeed, the alternative theoretical explanation that "G-d's Physics" offers to what appears to be a (direct) "material-causal" physical relationship between certain "massive-objects" and their "curvature of Space-Time" is based on this UCP's simultaneous computation of "more massive" objects as more "spatially-consistent" (e.g., as defined through the mentioned UCP's "Object-consistent" computational definition), relatively to "less-massive" objects – which therefore creates "high-mass"/"more spatially-consistent" regions within the series of UF's frames, as opposed to "low-mass"/"less spatially consistent" regions, which therefore seem to "disappear" or be "less spatially-consistent" relative to the "high-mass"/"more spatially-consistent" regions; which therefore gives the "impression" as if the more massive "high-mass"/"more spatially-consistent" "curve Space-Time" – but in truth, it is only the distribution of those "more massive"/"more spatially-consistent" regions which remain relatively constant" across the given series of UF's frames, as opposed to the distribution of the other "less-massive"/"less spatially-consistent" regions around the (former) "more massive"/"more spatially-consistent", which gives the "appearance" of the "curvature of Space-Time" by certain "massive objects"! Somewhat similarly, the profound new explanation of "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Paradigm for the Four basic Forces of Nature – which for the first time in Physics successfully unifies between all of them, e.g., and not just between Three of them as explained in the "Standard Model"; and perhaps even more significantly, also unifies for the first time in Physics (history) between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – going beyond Einstein's General Relativity Theory's capacity to unify between "space" and "time" (as the four dimensional "Space-Time" continuum), between "energy" and "mass" (as the " $E=Mc^2$ " Energy-Mass Equivalence), and connect "mass" with "Space-Time" as "curving Space-Time"; the new "G-d's Physics" explanation for the complete unification of those Four Forces as well as of the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") is based on the abovementioned novel "Universal Computational Formula" indicating the UCP's simultaneous computation of those four basic physical features for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) based on the UCP's new computational definitions derived from the UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computations! In this manner, the novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) offers an entirely new (and profound) understanding of the "composition", "true nature", and "dynamics" of the entire physical universe! This is because through its realization that the UCP necessarily has to compute (simultaneously) the four basic physical features for each exhaustive spatial pixel - since they represent "integrative-complimentary" facets of the UCP singular computation of the degree of "consistency" or "inconsistency", e.g., pertaining to any exhaustive spatial pixel relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "internal composition" of any such given spatial pixel ("object") we realize that what seemed to be those four basic "independent" physical features, e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" are in truth but different "complimentary-integrative" computational by-products of the same singular higher-ordered UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixels' "frame"/"object" – "consistent"/"inconsistent"! In this manner, "G-d's Physics" new "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) was shown capable of unifying the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") as "complimentary-integrative" computational facets of the same singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)! Likewise, it was shown that the Four basic Forces of Nature ("Weak"/"Strong Nuclear" forces, "Electromagnetic" and "Gravitational" Forces) can also be derived from this singular UCP's "Universal

Computational Formula" based on the recognition that the three "Energy-related" Forces mentioned, i.e., "Weak/Strong Nuclear" and "Electromagnetic" Forces are computed by the singular UCP as different "frame"- "inconsistent" energy computations, whereas the Fourth "Gravitational Force" is computed by the UCP as "object-consistent" "mass-related" computation, as explained above and previously; But since all these Four Forces are derived from the same singular UCP's UCF through the UCP's computation of "frame"- "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") integrative-complimentary computations, they are all integrated as part of the UCP's singular computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)! In this manner, it is understood that there cannot exist any "independent" physical features, or "independent" Forces or "independent" relativistic and quantum elements because all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe are computed simultaneously by this singular higher-ordered UCP in terms of their "frame"/"object" – "consistent"/"inconsistent" computations! Indeed, this singular UCP's UCF has been also shown to completely integrate all quantum and relativistic features as integral elements within the same singular higher-ordered UCP's computation, as can be glanced from the two respective "Relativistic/ Quantum Formats" of the UCP: This UCF embeds key Relativistic and Quantum relationships (and laws) within this singular (novel) UCF (e.g., The Relativistic "Energy-Mass Equivalence", and Quantum "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's Complimentary Pairs") as can be seen from the UCF's two (respective) Relativistic and Quantum Formats: UCF's Relativistic Format: $e \times s/t = m \times (c^2/h)$ UCF's Quantum Format: $t \times m \times (c^2/h) = s \times e$ We therefore realize that the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm metamorphosizes our basic understanding of the basic nature and dynamics of both the relativistic and quantum realms; wherein it is understood that there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s, e.g., at either the quantum or relativistic levels, but rather that the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This also implies that the basic "material-causal" assumption standing at the basis of the "Standard Model" has to be challenged and negated: The subatomic realm does not operate based on the existence of "independent-particles" which interact with each other, thereby producing certain quantum phenomena, as well as giving rise to the Three Forces (abovementioned)! This is because as stipulated (above and previously), there cannot exist any such "material-causal" direct or indirect physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in any single or multiple UF's frames – e.g., due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's. Moreover, we've already seen that the even the existence of "independent" or "separate" relativistic or "quantum" elements is negated based on the New "G-d's Physics" UCF, since it points at the simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein replacing the "Standard Model" is "G-d's Physics" New (profound) understanding that the universe does not operate through- or is not based upon- the existence of any "subatomic particles" – but is rather permeated and continuously being created- "dissolved"- recreated- and evolved- solely through the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe at every minimal "time-point" (e.g., producing the extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" at the unfathomable rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ "!) b). The "UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula": Indeed, this new profound realization of the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm wherein the universe does not exist as a "solid-material" entity, nor does it operate based on any direct- or indirect- "material-causal" physical interactions between

any number of "subatomic-particles" (as assumed by the "Standard Model"), nor are the Four basic Forces underlie by such direct or indirect "material-causal" interactions between such "elementary particles"(!); but is rather solely explained through the UCP's singular higher-ordered continuous (simultaneous) computation- "dissolution"- recreation- and evolution- of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the physical universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!"); inevitably led to the discovery of the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD-UCF) "expanded" format of the abovementioned UCF! As explicated and delineated previously: c). "G-d's Physics" Novel "Computational Table"! We now reach the culmination of "G-d's Physics" complete new description of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal time point's" extremely rapid series of UF's (e.g., " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!") This new profound understanding and description of the physical universe comprises an understanding that one the once hand, due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s, there cannot exist any "material-causal" (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any number of subatomic particles at any single or multiple UF's frame/s – thereby negating the Standard Model's basic underlying "Material-Causal" assumption; but, on the other hand, precisely due to the "mechanics" of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising each such consecutive UF's frame/s through the (abovementioned) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD-UCF) it is understood that the "apparent composition" of the entire physical universe by "elementary particles" must conform to- and be "comprised of"- this THCD-UCF computational definition and properties! In other words, even though the entire physical universe cannot include any direct or indirect "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – hence cannot operate through any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any number of "elementary particles"; nevertheless, the UCP's continuous computation- "dissolution"- re-creation- and evolution- of all such "elementary particles" is strictly based on this novel ("expanded") THCD-UCF computational definitions, and accompanying (previously delineated) computational definitions of the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features (for each exhaustive spatial pixel simultaneously for every consecutive UF's frame/s!):

We therefore inevitably reach the discovery of the novel "UCP's THCD-UCF's Computational Table"! which for the first time in Physics unifies all apparently "elementary particles" based on their mutual (necessary) computation by the singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., based on the THCD-UCF! Essentially, this THCD-UCF formulates (and constrains) the possible computational relationships between the four basic physical features of every subatomic particle, which therefore predicts- and explains- every existent- as well as every prospective- subatomic particle, thereby giving rise to the novel "UCP's THCD-UCF Computational Table"; Specifically, it is predicted that every existent (e.g., discovered) or prospective (e.g., to be discovered) subatomic particle would conform to the UCF's stipulated computational relationships between the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – alongside the above outlined computational definitions of each of these four physical features!

Dedication

This article is dedicated to Rabbi Yosssef Yizhak ("Harayyaz") whose Yortzeit occurs today, Yud Shevat, and the Lubavitcher Rabbi who's Vision, Life-work and Mission is to bring the World towards the fulfillment of the "Geulah Perfected State of the World".

A. Resolution of the Apparent GRT-QM Theoretical Inconsistency

Perhaps the key unresolved "enigma" in Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics is the "*Gravitational Enigma*" (GE), i.e.: *Deciphering the under-*

lying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can:

a) Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion that is not based on the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected even after two full decades of intensive experimentation?!); c) Unify between the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the "curvature of Space-Time" by "massive objects" (e.g., based on the G-D'S PHYSICS' New Scientific "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm); Thus far, the "Gravitational Force" has been explained based on GRT's key assumption wherein this "Gravitational Force" (GF) is responsible for the "curvature of Space-Time" – i.e., without actually explaining its underlying "nature". Moreover, this assumed GF remains "inexplicable" (and "independent") of the Standard Model's proven capacity to unify between those other Three Forces, based on the discovery of elementary subatomic particles' interactions, and therefore is seen an unresolved "Gravitational Enigma"?! The purpose of this article is to try and offer an alternative solution for this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) based on the discovery of a New "G-d's Physics" Scientific Paradigm [1-30].

The potential capacity of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm to resolve this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c2/h" = 1.36-50 sec!), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! Additionally, the UCP's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) across a series of (such) UF's frame/s yields the UCP's novel "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe) – as being computed by this singular UCP, based on its two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency! According to this (new) G-D'S PHYSICS explanation, the UCP (simultaneously) computes these four basic physical features – including the "mass" value of each exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) based on the four possible combinations of those "Framework" (e.g., "frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent") "Computational Dimensions": Such that the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" computations, as the "space" and "energy" values of any given spatial pixel (across a given series of UF's); and "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computations, as the "mass" and "time" values (across a given UF's series) (Figure 1):

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

FIGURE 1. UCP'S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Intriguingly, these novel "G-D'S PHYSICS" UCP's "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features also led to the discovery of an "Universal Computational Formula" (Figure 2), which was shown to completely integrate these four basic physical features as secondary computational "by-products" of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP (for the first time in Physics)!

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...n} [PxI (a...z)]

FIGURE 2. The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

The UCF's Relativistic Format:

$$\left. \begin{matrix} E * s \\ t \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{M * c^2}{h}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

$$\left. \begin{matrix} t * m \\ s * e \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{h * c^2}{c^2}$$

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs") are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS").

Significantly, the first (abovementioned) facet of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm's potential resolution of the GE's first component – i.e., a) Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can both unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); is given through this (singular

higher-ordered) UCP's (in-depth) analysis of the (true) "computational basis" of the "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM stems: According to the New G-D's PHYSICS's computational analysis, this "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" for the transmission of any "signal" (or even "information") across "space" and "time" – which seems to be "contradicted" by QM's "Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon", indicating that the measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the "complimentary" ("space/energy" or "mass/time") measurement of the other "entangled particle"?! But, according to the new CUT's Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and "resolution"- of this apparent "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from the UCP's singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all "Single Spatial-Temporal" computation ("SST"): "particle" of relativistic "object" (e.g., relating to only "one" spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), "Multi Spatial-Temporal" computation (MST): "wave" (e.g., relating to at least "two" points being measured at any point in time) or "Exhaustive Spatial Temporal" (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all "exhaustive" spatial pixels comprising an entire "Universal Frame", UF), across a series of UF's frames (Figure 3);

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+	3+

FIGURE 3. UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" COMPUTATIONS

B. The UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's)

"G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm discovered the existence of the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's):

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance

with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!?! Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת):

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past" - "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its latter "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's

Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfect Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah" may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Deborah"/"גבורה"):

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" in order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/"Tiferet"):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at: Sep. 7th & 8th, 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects

comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of **נצח** "Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"(תשובה)/"הוד"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva"/ "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("**נצח**"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("**נצח**"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of **הוד**/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("**יסוד**" "Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of **יסוד**/"Yesod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this **יסוד**/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State

necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("**כתר**"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) **יסוד**/"Yesod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or **כתר** / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this **כתר**/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the **כתר**/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("**כתר**"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown"))"; This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec') for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

C. "G-D's Physics" New "Gimatria", "Dynamic-Moral Principle" & "Geulah Driven" Universe!

We now reach the "culmination" of our new understanding of the physical universe, which is based on the entire corpus of over 100 scientific (peer-reviewed) articles dedicated to the discovery, delineation and empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics! We've already seen that the entire physical universe does not exist "continuously" or "independently" of its continuous "computation"- "dissolution"- "re-computation" and "development" by the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR); and in fact, that the entire physical universe may be viewed (or regarded) merely as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which exists only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed by this singular UCR: simultaneously for all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s), but "ceases" to exist, and "dissolves" back into the singularity or the UCP/UCR "in-between" any two consecutive

As also described in previous articles (Bentovish, see detailed References) the UCP's extremely rapid computation of the series of Universal Frames (and of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising it) is primarily based upon a few characteristics associated with the UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions and associated Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula (THCD's-UCF), including its delineation of the Gimatria's (alphabetic Hebrew numeric values associated with each letter comprising the Hebrew name of any given object or even person!) Generally speaking, we may describe the "extremely complex" and "infinitely intelligent" capacities of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (or UCR), there are "six layers" (or phases) of this singular UCP/UCR:

D. The UCP's Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's: "General Blueprint Universal Plan" (GCC, CMD, DEMP, GDD)

The Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's comprise the "General Blueprint Plan" for the UCP outlines the continuous "origination" - "sustenance" and "development" of the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of the universe, e.g., in which the singularity of the UCP will be recognized by Humanity (and Science) alongside its "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's existence and behavior! It therefore "contains" the key "Consistency Computational Principles" guiding the UCP's execution of the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' operation, as well as all other ensuing computations carried out by the next five successive levels of the UCP (delineated below); Generally speaking, it contains these "Computational Principles":

1) Consciousness-Moral Development (CMD)

Relates to the UCP's "General Guiding Principle" of "steering" the whole universe from its initial "inanimate" matter state through successive "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings – leading towards Humanity's Ultimate "Geulah Perfected Goal" state! (It should be mentioned that due to "G-D's Physics' Collective Human Consciousness Focus theoretical postulate and empirical validation of its unique UNCIARE "Critical Prediction" based on the abovementioned Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (CAGUARE), therefore this CMD Guiding Principle is also associated with "G-D's Physics' "Six Days' Creation Model", SDCM, as outlined above)

2) The "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP)

Another key "General Guiding Principle" is one of the THCD's called "the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP) which also characterizes one of the "sublime characteristics" of the UCP/UCR associated with its Moral nature! According to this DEMP, the UCP contains a "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" which comprises all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being based on his/her "Moral Choice/s" (at every point in time)! According to this UCP's DEMP ("Guiding Principle") whenever any individual human-being makes (for instance) any "immoral choice" ("G-d forbid") and inflicts "pain/suffering" upon another individual human-being, then this "triggers" the UCP's DEMP's "balancing moral computation" which computes an equivalent "negative situation" in which that individual human-being that "inflicted pain/suffering" upon another individual human-being would have to experience ("G-d forbid") an "equivalently negative situation" – that would most likely lead him/her to make "Teshuvah", (e.g., a Jewish term denoting a sincere sense of remorse and associated conscious decision not to repeat any such "immoral choice/s"! Indeed, as outlined above (and previously), to the extent that any such individual human-being makes such a sincere "Teshuvah" (also represented by the eighth HCD of "Teshuva" ("הוּד"), then this will "prevent" and (indeed) "omit" the UCP's ("need" to present) any subsequent "equivalent negative situation" UF's frame/s (for

that individual human-being), because the whole "purpose" of the UCP's execution of the DEMP is to "balance",

"correct" and "steer" each individual human-being towards a "morally-balanced" state of Humanity in which the whole of Humanity views and regards each other as "inseparable parts" of the same singular higher-ordered Moral "Universal Consciousness Reality"! (As noted previously, the same UCP's DEMP also "renumerates" each individual human-being by presenting an "equivalent-positive" situation for any "good moral choice/s" made by any individual human-being to assist another individual human-being as well!)

3) Geulah Directed Development (GDD)!

Perhaps the most important (key) "Guiding Principle" is the UCP's "Geulah-Directed Development" (GDD) of the whole physical universe – whose whole "pre-planning" by the singular higher-ordered UCP has been geared and directed to attain this "Ultimate-Geulah Goal Perfected State" of the universe! It therefore "overarches" and "leads" the other (abovementioned) two UCP's "Guiding Principles" – all aimed at fulfilling this UCP's (singular higher-ordered) "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal"! Therefore, we can see that this "germinal" "Geulah Perfected Goal" of the UCP (e.g., including its three abovementioned ensuing Consistency Computation elements of: CMD, DEMP & GDD).

E. The Seven Secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) "Geulah-Directed Universe"!

Based upon the TKI-HCCD's (three initial HCD's) "General Blueprint Plan" for the whole origination, sustenance and development of the universe then leads to the "secondary layer" of the "Seven Secondary HCD's" which are utilized by the UCP as its means for "executing" and "directing" the continuous development of the universe (e.g., and of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it!) – which are aimed at "steering" the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity & Science! As we can clearly see in the Diagram (and as outlined and delineated in previous articles), the Three Key Initial (TKI) HCD's provide us with a detailed "Geulah Directed Blueprint Plan for "steering" the universe towards this "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" – based on the (first HCD of the UCP's) "Wisdom/Free Will" "desire" to create the world (and specifically our planet Earth – filled with the various forms of inanimate matter, and animate: plants, animals, all leading to the creation of human-beings endowed with a unique conscious "Moral-Choice"!); subsequently, the second HCD of "Computation" also contains the UCP's "Consistency" CMD "germinal" conception (e.g., comprising the conception of the universe's whole entire development from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings and leading up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected" State! The next seven HCD's actually execute (and fulfill) the UCP's DEMP & GDD "Guiding Principles" (as previously delineated)! Succinctly stated, the fourth HCD of "Goodwill/DEMP" represents the UCP's DEMP's enables each individual human-being (e.g., as well as the whole of Humanity) to "balance" and in fact "enhance" his/her "Moral Stance", i.e., assisting Humanity (and each individual human-being comprising it) to realize our "inseparability" from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, and therefore "stop" and (principally) "negate" any "negative-immoral" action and in fact enhance (and "encourage") all "moral-good behavior" towards our fellow human-beings! The fourth HCD of "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" represents the actual execution of the UCP's "bank" of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" (e.g., contained within the whole corps of the "pre-planned course" of the universe's "Complete Journey" from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – and all of the "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being necessary in order to bring Humanity towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe! The sixth HCD of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah": CHCF-JRH) represents the UCP's

allocation of a single (whole) Jewish Year (segment) from the (previous "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" spanning the whole "preplanned corpus" of the entire universe's development) containing all of the necessary "events" and "situations" found within a single "Jewish Year" that are "pre-planned" to "execute" and "balance" the DEMP in order to "uplift" Humanity "ever-closer" to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal State" (e.g., during this New Jewish Year)! The seventh HCD of the "UCP's Computed Potential Object" relates (according to "G-D's Physics" previously delineated novel computational definitions of any given "Object's") two associated physical features of "mass" (i.e., "Object-consistent") and "time" (i.e., "Object-inconsistent")! This seventh UCP's HCD computation takes into account all previous UCP's HCD's cumulating any given "Object's" (e.g., any individual human-being's according to his/her "moral-choice/s", or any other "animate" or "animate" "Object's" associated moral value/s and ensuing DEMP's based computed "Object" ("mass" and "time" values)! Subsequently, the UCP's eighth HCD of "Teshuvah" (as outlined above) allows for the possibility of any individual human-being's making a sincere "teshuva" (e.g., as explained above and previously) – which then "alters" (and even "prevents") the UCP's presentation of any potentially "negative situation/s" for any given individual human-being based on such a (sincere) "teshuva" (by that individual human-being)! The ninth HCD of the "UCP's Actual Computed Object Four Physical Features" represents the UCP's culmination of the actual computation for the next (subsequent) UF's frame's computation of the four basic physical features (e.g., of "mass", "energy", "space" and "energy") – based on all of the previous eight HCD's! Note that this ninth UCP's "Actual Computed Object" – even though it contains also the two (additional) "Frame" related physical features, e.g., "Frame-consistent" ("space") and "Frame-inconsistent" ("energy") – it still "lacks" the actual ability to "materialize" any given exhaustive spatial pixel or any object (based upon these extremely complex and intelligent computations)!? According to "G-D's Physics THCD's detailed analysis, this requires the "infinite intelligence and power" of the UCP- which Itself "executes" and "carries out" this "materialization" of all exhaustive spatial pixels and objects in the universe (comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s) in the Tenth HCD's "UCP's 'Infinite' Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Materialization!" Indeed, as we will see in the accumulation of all the five detailed "layers" (or phases) of the UCP's singular (extremely complex) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (and objects) in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) far exceeds even our most "wild imagination" regarding the "infinite": "complexity", "intelligence" and "power" required in order to accumulate and integrate these "disparate" ("infinitely complex") five (integrated) lawyer of the UCP's (simultaneous) computation for each exhaustive spatial pixel/s in the universe!

It is important to note that "encapsulated" within the Seven Secondary HCD's are also found the Geulah Directed Development (GDD) – found within the "Good-Will" HCD; the entire "Conscious-Moral Development" (CMD) – found within the "Multi-Spatial-Temporal-Reservoir" (MSTR) containing the UCP's "reservoir" of all the UF's of the entire universe's "pre-planned history", i.e., corpus of all "past", "present" and "future" UF's frame/s, e.g., including its development from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe!)

F. Gimatria Based UCP's Computation of All Exhaustive Spatial Pixels' Objects!

Next, we have to add the UCP's (successive) computation of every exhaustive spatial object in the universe – in terms of the UCP's computation of its "physical characteristics" based on its Hebrew name's "Gimatria": i.e., alphabetic-numeric value/s comprised of each of its "five" (or less or more) letters which correspond to the (Seven Secondary HCD's) initial five HCD's: Good-Will (חסד), MSTR (גבורה), UNCIARE-JRH (תפארת), UCP's Potential Computed Object (נצח), Teshuva (הוד)! According to "G-D's Physics" novel conception of the manner in which the UCP "orig-

inates" all exhaustive objects in the universe (previously delineated) the UCP extremely rapid computation of the series of UF's (comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point") at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!" the UCP "allocates" "five zero's" out of the 50 zero's (e.g., power of minus 50!) – the first 5 zeroes are allocated to the UCP's computation of the given object's first (Seven Secondary HCD's) of "Good-Will" which is associated that object's first letter (e.g., as it is computed relative to the other four remaining letters in that five-letter object's name; if there are less- or more- than those five "template" Gimatria Based UCP's computation, then there is a "compensation" or "addition" by the missing letters that are added to the "missing" letters or "last fifth letter"!)

Thus, for instance the Hebrew word for a human-being is אדם which only contains three letters: the Gimatria alphabetic value of the first letter "א" is "1" – which is assigned to the first (Secondary Seven) HCD of "Good-Will" (חסד) which receives the highest value in terms of the "core characterization" of the "spiritual facet" underlying this object's subsequent Four Physical Features! If we were to give a metaphoric image to the manner in which these "Gimatria-based" alphabetic numeric vales are associated with groups of "five zero's" – for each of these five initial (Seven Secondary HCD's): Good-Will (חסד), MSTR (גבורה), UNCIARE-JRH (תפארת), UCP's Potential Computed Object (נצח), Teshuva (הוד) are subsequently translated into the Four Physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"); we could use the metaphor of "large babushka" the famous "Russian doll" that comprises up to 5 or 7 smaller (same image but smaller dolls) contained within this "large babushka" doll! If we imagine a scenario in which this whole "large babushka doll" is created from "within- outwardly"; i.e., beginning with the innermost smallest babushka doll, and then covering an enlarging and encapsulating this "smallest babushka doll" within ever growing "babushka-dolls"! we can notice a surprising "finding" – i.e., that even though the "smallest babushka doll" cannot be seen when it is encapsulated by all of the "larger babushka dolls", when we focus on the "shape" of the "large babushka doll" – we suddenly realize that it is (in fact) the initial "shape" (and "characteristics") of the "small babushka doll" that actually "molded" (and in fact "determined") the "shape" (and characteristics) of the "large babushka doll"! This is because (we realize) that each successive "larger babushka doll" has to "conform" and "replicate" (while "enlarging") the "original small babushka doll's shape"! This metaphor implies that there is a greater strength to the initial letters of any object's name – relative to its subsequent letters, which "mold" the basic "characteristics" of the "spiritual facets" of this object, e.g., in consideration: both of the special ("spiritual") elements of each Hebrew letter and its associated semantic meaning/s, its Gimatria numeric value and its association with one of the five initial (Seven Secondary HCD's, listed above – with the former HCD's bearing a "greater weight" in molding the "spiritual characteristics" of the given object's later physical features)! Thus, for instance, the abovementioned Hebrew word אדם possesses the first letter as "א" which carries out the "greatest weight" (e.g., alike the "smallest babushka" shaping the shape of the whole "big babushka doll" (subsequently)! This "א" Hebrew letter receives the Gimatria value of "1" – but this "1" digit can be viewed as representing the highest value of the "fifty zero's" (e.g., "possessing the value of many "trillions" of times per second – and indeed appearing in all of the "larger babushka dolls", that is "appearing in all of the fifty zero's UF's) This "א" letter also represents symbolically "G-D" as it is also the beginning of the word "G-D" in Hebrew: אלוהים! Finally, this first letter "א" is also associated with the first (Secondary Seven HCD's) of "Good-Will" implying that this "אדם" word signifies a great degree of "Divine-Good-Will"! In contrast, the second letter in this word "ד" has a higher Gimatria value of "4" and is associated with the second (of the Seven Secondary HCD's) which represents the "gevurah" the spiritual left side of "judgement" and "measurement" as signified by the "Multi-Spatial-Temporal Reservoir"... Interestingly the third letter is "ם" which has Gimatria numeric value of 40! and also represents the middle letter (or conjoining element) of the whole alphabet, with a special "spiritual" element of completion and wisdom (like Moses' 40 days on Mt. Sinai at which he received the Holy Torah (Bible)!

Interestingly also the combination of the two last letters are "ט-ם" semantic meaning is the Hebrew word for "blood"; so a partial understanding of the "spiritual nature" of the Hebrew word for a human-being points at it signifying a strong "Divine-Goo-Will" together with a "less-strong" (but still significant) element of "judgement", "bodily", "measured" elements – and the need (or efforts) to "combine" between these apparently "disparate" influences, alongside a strong element of "Wisdom" and "Perfection"! Another interesting point to note is that those "five zero's" allocated by the UCP's computation to the "length of time" and "order" in which the UCP computes each of these five (Seven Secondary HCD's) it is suggested – represents the fact that for each of these "five-template letters" takes into account each of the other four remaining letters and it affected by them (for each word, e.g., with shorter or longer words possibly missing or having redundant repetitions in terms of their usage of those five-template letter structure of the UCP's fifty zero's computation)!

G. Four Physical Features UCP's Computation

The next phase or layer in the UCP's computation of all exhaustive objects involves the "translation" of the Seven Secondary HCD's & associated Gimatria's (e.g., of those five secondary HCD's) "spiritual nature" (described above) into the Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time")! Hence, the UCP translates each one of the five mentioned HCD's "spiritual nature" (e.g., associated with its specific HCD nature as well as the abovementioned Gimatria analysis etc. elements) into the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"! As can be seen from the Diagram, once again the UCP's "allocation" of "four zero's" for each one of these five HCD's amounts in "twenty-zero's" is associated with this translation into the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mas" and "time")!

The UCP's "Infinite" – THCD's "Materialization" (6th Physical Feature: 47th-50th)

The concluding phase of the UCP's computation of each exhaustive spatial pixel and object in the whole universe relates to the UCP's "materialization" of each object based on the sixth HCD of the "UCP's Actual Computed Object 4 Physical Features", which summates and cumulates all of the abovementioned 20 zero's HCD's four corresponding physical features input into the four general physical features for each exhaustive object which the UCP computes! It is important to note that given the almost "Infinite complexity" of the necessary computation for every exhaustive object (in the universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s) – not only in terms of the four physical features, but also taking into consideration the other (abovementioned) facets of the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (e.g., including for instance the DEMP's need to "balance" and "correct" any "immoral action/s" made by any given individual human-being by producing the equivalent "negative situation" for that individual in order for him/her to make a sincere "teshuvah"!) Therefore, it is suggested that that the "Infinite" of the UCP (itself) is necessary and involved in the Tenth "UCP's Infinite Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Materialization! [47-50] in order to "materialize" any exhaustive object in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)!

One of the most fundamental changes that is brought about by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is the key understanding that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" of "different" UF's frame/s)! This is simply due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' (four associated basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") for each consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe (e.g., and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s back into the singularity of the UCP)! As outlined previously, if the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), then there cannot exist any (di-

rect or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s (or relationship/s) between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (at any consecutive UF's frame/s)! Moreover, since all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP ("in-between") any two consecutive UF's frame/s, therefore there also cannot exist any physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels across any two ("consecutive" or even "non-consecutive" UF's frame/s)!

This profound new realization discovered through "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm undermines and negates the most basic "material-causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm: Thus, for instance the basic "Big-Bang" Model associated with the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT was negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! According to the "Big-Bang" Model, the whole creation of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event which created all of the suns, galaxies, planets, space, time, energy and mass in the universe!? But, since according to the New "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's "simultaneously" computes all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s), and the completely "dissolves" all such exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., back into itself) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; therefore, there could not have existed any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising this (purely hypothetical) "Big-Bang" initial nuclear event! This is because there could not have existed any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising this (initially assumed) "Big-Bang" nuclear event (at any single or multiple UF's frame/s)!? And (anyway) the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames, so that there cannot "develop" any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such (purely hypothetical initial) "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its creation of any "suns", "galaxies", "space", "mass" or "energy" etc.!?

The "Infinite Nature" of the "Universal Consciousness Reality"!

We now come to a "pivotal transformative point" in Physics' basic understanding of the "Infinite" of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which underlies – and in fact even "manifests" as the entire physical universe, but yet "transcends" it (i.e., "Infinitely")! This is because when we begin examining each of the multifarious facets of the UCR's continuous computation- "dissolution"- "sustenance"- and "development"- of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel/s comprising the entire physical universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec!) towards this UCP's/UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal State"; we immediately realize that the only manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCR could continuously "compute", "dissolve", "sustain" and "develop" each and every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (simultaneously at the abovementioned incredible rate) – as "guided" by the UCP's/UCR's "Pre-planned Geulah Driven Blueprint Plan" is only based on this UCR's "Infinite Nature"!

In order to elucidate this "Infinite Nature" of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, lets focus (separately) upon each of the various facets of this UCP/UCR "Consistency Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" various derived computations that are all necessary in order to allow this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR to compute the next subsequent UF's frame/s (e.g., at this "incredible" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50}$ sec!) (see Figure 1??) First, let's focus on the UCP's "Consistency-Gimatria" based computation of all exhaustive objects in the universe – for every consecutive UF's frame/s!? As delineated in previous articles, "G-D's Physics" new understanding of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR computes (simultaneously) all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for

every consecutive UF's frame at the "unfathomable" rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 sec!) – specifically in terms of its four basic physical features (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") is derived from its "Gimatria" based computation of the five basic Hebrew letters' alphabetic-numeric value for each given object's Hebrew name (which alongside its "semantic" meaning, including "smaller" comprising semantic units or words contained within each given Hebrew name, as previously delineated); This is based upon the UCP's "infinitely complex" computation of those five basic (initially ordered) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) of "Goodwill" (חסד), "Conscious-Moral Development" (CMD) ("גבורה"), "UNCIARE-JRH & DEMP" ("תפארת"), "UCP's Computed Potential Object" ("נצה"), UCP's "Teshuva" ("הוד") Gimatria based computation of the Four Physical Features (4PF'a):

Indeed, the UCP's/UCR's "Infinitude" – e.g., even only in terms of its computation of those "Gimatria" based computation of the five-basic (initial HCD's) template letters of each given Hebrew name, which is being translated into the Four Physical Features computation of the specific value/s (e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" for every exhaustive object in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 sec!) in utterly "incomprehensible"! When we take into account the greater "infinite" complexity of the this UCP's/UCR's computation the "UCP's Consistency" other facets of the "Conscious-Moral Development", "Dynamic Equilibrium Principle" (DEP) and "Geulah Driven Development" – we cannot but stand "perplexed", "astonished" (and indeed at a great "awe"), when we consider the utter "Infinitude" of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! This is because we begin realizing that when we look at any of the "infinite" atoms, quarks etc. comprising any single or multiple object in the universe, as well as the whole vast and "infinite" regions of the universe's expanse; and we take into account that just for the "static" "existence" and "sustenance" of the universe and all of its multifarious "infinite" exhaustive spatial pixels – it is necessary for this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR "Infinitude" to compute each such exhaustive spatial pixel's "existence", "dissolution", "re-computation" (and "development") "simultaneously" at the incredible rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 sec!

But, when we "add" into this "infinite computational complexity" the fact that each of these exhaustive spatial pixels is also undergoing a "continuous development" originated by this singular UCP/UCR – for instance, through the UCP's "CMD" involves a "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of the UCP that includes all of the universe's development – from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings: all assumed to have been computed and created in a mere "six days" (e.g., due to "G-D's Physics" Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) postulate and the universe's (otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion", previously delineated); and the whole of the universe's development throughout its "history" – leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe, which Humanity (and Science in now entering with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm), in which Science recognizes the singularity of the UCP/UCR, alongside its "intrinsic sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (which therefore affects and describes Humanity's "existence" and "behavior") If we are just to "imagine" the "infinite complexity" of the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" of the whole development of the universe's history including its "macroscopic development" from "inanimate": matter, through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and also its unique "specific objects' development" (pattern/s): Thus, for instance, we know that each unique "object", i.e., whether it be "inanimate matter" (of any specific type: atoms, subatomic particles, chemical compounds etc.) or even more so: "animate": plants, animals or human-beings possesses a unique characteristic for its "life-span development"! This means, that the UCP's "infinitely complex" computation of

all "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings (e.g., "simultaneously" throughout Earth's different environments etc.) must "remember", "sustain", "dissolve" and "re-compute" and "develop" each particular Biological specie – based on its specific pattern of development across its full life-span, i.e., for an unfathomable number of Biological species and specific organisms (plants, animals or human-beings)!

We must bear in mind that not only has the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm proven empirically to more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" (e.g., based upon the direct empirical validation of G-D's Physics above-mentioned two unique "Critical Predictions" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions!); but more fundamentally, the basic "Material-Causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm, e.g., assuming that everything in the universe (either at the "macroscopic" Relativistic level or at the "microscopic subatomic" levels) operates based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between a (finite) number of constituting material elements – was principally negated both based upon "G-D's Physics' New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, which asserts that there cannot exist any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" - or "different" - UF's frame/s, e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of this singular UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! In addition, "G-D's Physics" discovery of the (profound) "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) was (previously) shown (more fundamentally) to "principally negate" the very basic "Computational Structure" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm! This is because this (novel) CDP indicated that underlying this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm there exists a basic "Self-Referential Computational System" Computational Structure which inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" that are contradicted through the CDP – i.e., instead leading to the inevitable recognition of the singular higher-ordered UCP which (alone) can simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s!

So, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the basic "Material-Causal" assumption of the Old Paradigm must be strictly negated (e.g., as shown above and previously, due to "G-D's Physics New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm and its novel CDP theoretical postulate) – in favor of the CDP's discovered (and empirically validated) identification of the singular higher-ordered UCP's continuous (simultaneous) "computation"- "dissolution"- "re-computation"- and "development" of all exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable" rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 !) This means that as we've begun seeing (above) the UCP's (simultaneous) computation of all "inanimate" and particularly "animate": plants, animals and human-beings involves an "Infinitude" of its computational complexity: to "remember", "sustain", "dissolve" and then "re-compute" and "develop" every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" values) for each individual plant, animal and human-being (simultaneously at this "unfathomable" rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36-50 !) In other words, since according to "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) New Scientific Paradigm, this singular higher-ordered UCP has "Pre-planned" the "Blueprint Plan" for the universe's entire development – e.g., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (i.e., as mentioned above and delineated previously occurring within the UCP's "Six Days Creation Model" due to the CHCF postulate and the CAGUARE's otherwise "unexplained" phenomenon!?) also "guides" the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, as can be seen from Figure 1 and Diagram 1; that the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s is dependent upon the "Three Initial

Key" (TIK) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's), in which the whole development of the entire physical universe has been "Pre-planned" (from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, as mentioned above), which is also executed through the UCP's "Consistency" computation's (abovementioned) "Conscious-Moral Development"! This means that the UCP has to simultaneously compute "anew" for each consecutive UF's frame/s all "inanimate" matter's composition, i.e., once again: "remember", "sustain", "dissolve", "re-compute" and "develop" each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, in terms of its four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"); and even exponentially more "infinitely complex" is the UCP's computation of every exhaustive "animate" object – based on its (abovementioned "Gimatria" alphabetic numeric translation into those Four basic Physical Features) and the "Infinite" of the UCP's computation of every specific animate entity: particular plant (e.g., including the vast differences between an algae and say a huge Sequoia Tree!?), every exhaustive Biological animal species and every individual human-being – in terms of their particular "life-span development" characteristics at every "trillionth of a trillionth etc." (e.g., " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}!$ ")

Indeed, our recognition of the utter "Infinite" (capacities) of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR becomes even more apparent when we add into our understanding of the manner in which this UCP/UCR computes, sustains and develops the entire physical universe – the (abovementioned) "UCP's Consistency – DEMP" computation! This is because (as previously delineated) the UCP's DEMP essentially implies that (due to the UCP's "intrinsic-sublime" "All-Goodness" and "Moral" characteristic), the UCP's DEMP "balances" and "enhances" any given individual human-being's "moral-choice/s" – leading Humanity towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal", e.g., by "teaching" each individual human-being that it is truly "inseparable" from the "Oneness", "Peace", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" of this singular higher-ordered UCP! The UCP accomplishes this "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" through the DEMP's "balancing" of any individual human-being's selection of ("G-D forbid") "immoral action/s" towards another human-being instigated through the UCP's selection of an "equivalent-negative" situation in which that individual human being who ("G-D forbid") inflicted "pain"/"suffering" upon another individual human-being will have to experience the same "negative situation", so that he/she may make a sincere "teshuva", e.g., real "remorse" over the "wrong-doing" or "immoral action" they've done. Conversely, if any individual human-being have opted to "assist" or (otherwise) "act-morally" towards another individual human-being, then equally this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR will select an "equivalently-positive" situation, in which this "assisting" (moral-actioned) individual human-being will also have the "privilege" of experiencing such an "equivalently-positive" situation in which (most likely) that "other human-being" which he/she assisted will assist or bestow "goodness" upon himself/herself? As delineated previously, the manner in which this UCP's DEMP "operates" is based upon the existence of the UCP's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" comprising all possible "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" or each individual human-being (possessing a free moral choice)! This implies that this singular higher-ordered UCP has to compute for each individual human-being (at any "trillionth of a trillionth of a second etc.") the precise "situation" would allow that particular individual human-being to experience the "same" ("negative" or "positive" situation/s) in which that individual human-being ("G-D forbid") inflicted "pain/suffering" upon another human-being, so that this "negative-immoral situation" will lead that individual human-being to undertake a sincere "teshuva" (e.g., deep "remorse" and conscious decision not to repeat any such "wrong-doing"! But, this means that this singular (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR has to (simultaneously) compute for each of the over eight Billion individual human-beings (existing today) the DEMP's "balancing" of all of their previous "moral/immoral action/s" taken throughout their lives – while taking into consideration all of the "other human-beings" that were involved in their "moral/immoral action/s" at

any point/s in time in their lives, and consequently compute (at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}!$ ") every consecutive UF's frame/s that would "balance" any "immoral action/s" (e.g., acted upon "against" any specific individual human-being) by creating the same "equivalent negative" situation (e.g., most likely by "reversing" the situation so that the "injured other person" will "reproduce" the same "negative situation" so as to have the "injuring person" experience "G-D forbid" the same "negative-immoral" situation, or by "reinforcing" and "remunerating" any "positive moral-action" by any Individual human being (towards another human being) which necessitates the UCP's "reinforcement" or "remuneration" of this "positive-moral action" of that individual human being through the UCP's computation of all those "equivalent positive situation/s" in which the "good-moral actor" (human-being) is being "rewarded" (or "encouraged"/"remunerated") for his/her "right-moral choice"! In both cases, it is likely that the UCP's/UCR's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s will compute the "Infinitely complex" (abovementioned) "moral-balancing" for each individual human-being – i.e., as "coupled" with those particular individual human-being/s that he or she have acted in a "moral" or "immoral" manner at each "(minimal) time-point" along the course of their entire live/s, in order to compute (e.g., create) the "equivalently-positive/negative" situation (i.e., with those particular individual human-beings which that given individual human-being interacted (in a "positive"- or "negative" – moral action/s), in order to "morally-balance" or "morally enhance" each individual human-being (out of the over eight Billion individual human-beings living on the Planet Earth)!??

If this is not "infinitely-complex"(enough), we must take into consideration the significance of the UCP's "teshuva" HCD's which allows for each (such) Individual human-being to make a sincere "teshuva" (as explained above) in which case the UCP will "avert" and "omit" the UCP's (preceding) "Computed Potential Object" ("צורה") – i.e., "equivalent negative situation" UF's situation, for each individual human-being (e.g., with his/her "coupled other human-being" towards which the "immoral action" was conducted, "G-D forbid"! Indeed, it is utterly "amazing" and "awe-inspiring" to realize the UCP's/UCR's "Infinite" – having to compute not only the "infinitely complex" computation for each of Humanity's (eight Billion human-beings), but also to take into consideration within this "Infinite" of the UCP's computation also the degree to which each of these (eight Billion individual human-beings) has undertaken a sincere "teshuva" (towards any single or multiple other individual human-beings), and the manner in which this "Infinitely complex" UCP's computation alters the UCP's "Computed Potential Object's" (e.g., potentially "equivalent negative situation" into an "equivalent positive situation") for the subsequent "Actual Computed Object" HCD's for each individual human being (out of the over eight Billion individual human-beings!) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" (empirically validated) New Scientific Paradigm, due to this "Infinite" complexity of the UCP's/UCR's simultaneous computation of the DEMP – for each of the over eight Billion Individual human-beings (living today on our Planet), the direct involvement of this "Infinite UCR/UCP" in executing the actual "materialization" of the next subsequent UF's frame (e.g., at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}!$ ") at the tenth HCD's of the "UCP's Infinite Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions".

H. Earth's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) Functional Epicenter of the Universe!

One of the key differences between the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm and the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is the "Centrality of Human Consciousness" – i.e., in "space" and "time", and its intimate connection with the "Universal Consciousness Reality's" (UCR's) "Geulah Driven Universe" (GDU)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm, it seems that "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) plays a major role in the "Universe's Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIA-

RE)! As we've already seen, there is clear (and direct) empirical evidence for the centrality of this CHCF in terms of its UNCIARE's acceleration in the universe! As outlined above, in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept (e.g., which has been negated both based on the experimental failure to detect its existence experimentally, and "G-D's Physics" principle computational negation of its associated Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's SRCS Computational Structure!) – which assumes that this (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept can only account for a "constant-rate" expansion rate of the universe; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm points at an increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., "UNCIARE" due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", which occurs during the Jewish Rosh Hashanah's (two days' special) time-interval! Indeed, it has been proven empirically (above) that it is solely based on this CHCF that the universe's rate of expansion "increases over time", e.g., as indicated by the (otherwise unexplained) "Universe's Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UCAGUARE)!; An even more direct (further) validation of the centrality of the CHCF was called for Astronomers to validate during the upcoming two days' Jewish Rosh Hashanah – during September 16th & 17th 2023, in which it is predicted that the universe's rate of expansion will significantly increase (and continue to increase) during the whole ensuing Jewish year, relative to the universe's measured rate of expansion in the preceding time prior to Sep. 16-17th!? Moreover, previously it's been shown that this same CHCF may be responsible for the Centrality of Human Consciousness – not just in "time" but also in "space"! This relates to the otherwise "unexplained" empirically validated phenomenon wherein the Astronomical measurement of the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (UARE) also indicates that planet Earth stands at the center of this UARE! In other words, it may be the case wherein the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion – i.e., related to "space", wherein it is only relative to planet Earth's position that this accelerated rate of expansion pertaining to the furthest regions of space (wherein the farther any galactic element exists relative to planet Earth the faster its measured acceleration would be)! If (for instance) it is found that such equivalent Astronomical measurements of the UARE – do not yield the same "symmetrical increase" in the universe's UARE then this would validate the centrality of planet Earth (and its associated centrality of this CHCF) – in "space", as well as in "time"! "G-D's Physics" Novel CHCF's Center of the Universe Hypothesis! We therefore reach an "astounding" new Hypothesis of "G-D's Physics", i.e., hypothesizing that at the center of the universe's existence, dynamics and development – stand our planet Earth due to this CHCF, including the rotation of our sun (around it) and the accelerated expansion of other galactic elements "emanating" from planet Earth's CHCF! This is because once we realize that the evolution of the physical universe cannot be explained merely due to an any initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event- e.g., based on the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm (above); and that (in fact), the basic SRCS Computational Structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm was shown to be negated by "G-D's Physics" (novel) "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) – i.e., as inevitably leading to both "logical-inconsistency" and (ensuing) "computational indeterminacy" that are both negated by the CDP's insistence upon the (proven) capacity of this apparently SRCS Computational System to determine the accelerated expansion of the universe – which (according to the CDP) points at the singularity of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/ Consciousness Principle" (UCP) as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)! And most significantly, empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" (above) unique "Critical Prediction" regarding the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) – as more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's assumed "constant rate" of the universe's expansion rate! Therefore, we must negate (and reject) the Old "Material-Causal" GRT's Paradigm's assumption wherein the entire physical uni-

verse has been created (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, and that its accelerated rate of expansion can be explained through the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept (which has been negated based on the three abovementioned considerations)!? The alternative (novel) explanation offered by the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- and development- of the whole physical universe is solely based on the operation of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that (solely) exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely responsible for the computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"!); And specifically, as associated with this UCP's connection with the CHCF – which brings about the UCP's initiation of the UNCIARE (empirically validated) phenomenon! In other words, the UNCIARE empirically validated phenomenon (unequivocally) proves that the origination of the entire physical universe, and its accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion", CAGUARE) is brought about by the UCP's consecutive computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s – and specifically by the CHCF's UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., assumed to take place at every Annual "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah" two days' time-interval (i.e., this year this will take place during Sep. 16-17th 2023 and onwards in which it is predicted the rate of the universe's expansion will increase significantly, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to the 16-17th – which I've called Astronomers and Cosmologists to test experimentally!) Indeed, once we realize that the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s and that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s; and therefore that the only "force" that creates- "dissolves"- re-creates- and evolves- any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is this singular higher-ordered UCP; hence, based on the clear empirical evidence indicating an UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion associated with the CHCF (hypothesized to take place during the Jew Rosh Hashanah!) we reach the inevitable theoretical conclusion wherein the expansion of the entire physical universe depends upon the CHCF – which brings about this UNCIARE increase in the universe's expansion rate (beginning in each Jewish Rosh Hashanah and continuing throughout the entire subsequent Jewish Year). We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion wherein taking together these two empirically validated facts: a) Empirical Validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which according to G-D's Physics is associated with the CHCF (e.g., specifically during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" special two days' time interval, as noted above: a call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test this UNCIARE-JRH during the upcoming Sep. 16th-17th, 2023 & onwards!) In other words, this UNCIARE (JRH) empirically confirmed phenomenon points at the centrality of CHCF "in time", i.e., specifically during the JRH (e.g., to be directly confirmed through the above call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test during the upcoming JRH!) b) Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! The empirically observed "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion")CAGUARE (indicates that the rate of the universe's expansion has increased (significantly) from its early "Background Radiation" stage to the current (increased) rate in the universe's expansion!? This phenomenon is associated with Planet Earth's "Epicenter" of the universe – in "space" (e.g., based on the fact that the accelerated rate of our regions of the universe is proportional to the distance from "Earth")! Taken together, these empirically validated (major otherwise "unexplained") phenomena point at the centrality of Earth's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" – in "space" and "time": as the (functional) center of the universe! It also reinforces the singularity of the higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" as the sole source "origi-

ning” the entire physical universe (at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec’)!)

I. "G-D's Physics" Redefinition of the Universe's Four Physical Features as Part of a "Geulah-Driven Development" Universe!

We thus reach the culmination of this "Synopsis" of "G-D's Physics" Redefinition of the Universe's Four (basic) Physical Features – based on "G-D's Physics" profound new understanding of both the "true nature" of the entire physical universe – which is the singular ("computationally-invariant") "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP), e.g., that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s (exhaustive spatial pixels), as well as (solely exists) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe!); And of the "Geulah Driven Development" (GDD) "steering" the entire physical universe (e.g., by this singular higher-ordered UCR) towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State!

Indeed, our whole understanding of the "origin" - "sustenance" - "development" - and "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of the universe changes ("dramatically") based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm; this is because in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal Random" (MCR) Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory" (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) which assumed that every phenomenon (or entity) in the universe can be explained merely based on (direct or indirect) physical interaction/s between a "finite" set of material entities, e.g., such as for instance the "creation" of the entire physical universe – which is assumed to be "caused" by an initial "nuclear event" (which is assumed to have created all of the suns, galaxies, mass and energy in the universe); the New "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm (for Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics) asserts that since this singular (higher-ordered) UCP/UCR "simultaneously" computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s; and all of these exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolve" back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s), there cannot exist any such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" (random) physical interaction/s at any given (single or multiple) UF's frame/s! Instead, the whole composition of the entire physical universe – including every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it, is solely computed by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR for each consecutive UF's frame/s! Moreover, as shown (above and previously), based on those two (novel and profound) "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulates of "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm we begin understanding that the physical universe – does not exist as an "independent-solid" reality, but rather only exists as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality", which solely exists "continuously", "uniformly" and "invariantly" both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also exists (without the presence of any physical universe!) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, we realized that the only manner in which the universe "exists" (e.g., apparently "continuously"!?) is based on the "incessant" computation of this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP! But, this profound new realization also pushed us to examine the basic (profound) characteristics of this singular UCR, i.e., its "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's) and associated "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) – which integrates (for the first time in Physics) between the Four basic Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") within a singular formula! Succinctly stated, this new THCD's UCF points at the UCP's/UCR's continuous "steering" of the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State, i.e., in which all of Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR, alongside its profound characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (thereby affecting and characterizing Humanity's behavior and existence!)

J. A "Geulah-Driven" Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion?!) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF's frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time", e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

We therefore begin realizing that the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe is driven by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe in order to reach that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! We realize that since the UCP is the sole "computationally-invariant" Principle (or "reality") that can "produce"- "sustain"- "dissolve"- or "evolve" any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, as well as "originate"- "sustain" and "evolve" the entirety of the physical universe! And moreover, since that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is continuously "originating"- "evolving"- ("dissolving"-) and "developing" the entire physical universe – is "motivated" by this singular higher-ordered UCP's/UCR's intrinsic "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", and geared towards fulfilling the Universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" State of the Universe (and of Humanity)! Therefore, we are "astonished" to find out that at every "trillionth-of-trillionth etc." of a second (e.g., " $c^2/h = 1.36-50 \text{ sec}!$ ") this UCP computes and evolves every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – including all human-beings, animals, plants and even "inanimate matter" based upon the UCP's THCD's (and associated THCD's-UCF!) which is "steering" the universe (and Humanity) towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and begin living in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

The important point to be noted (here) is that we begin noticing that the manner in which this UCP computes- sustains- ("dissolves"-) and evolves- every exhaustive spatial pixel (as well as the entirety of the whole universe) relies upon its THCD's extremely rapid computation, e.g., at the rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36-50 \text{ sec}!$ " in which the "Human Collective Consciousness Focus" (as well as the Individual Human Consciousness Moral Choice/s) plays a key central role, alongside this singular higher-ordered UCP's "steering" of Humanity and the Universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! This is because, when we closely examine those THCD's we notice two very important elements:

a) The sixth Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of the Universe's Expansion (NCARUE) at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH) – determines the universe's increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion, i.e., beginning at each JRH's two days' special time-interval! (This year the UNCIARE-JRH took place during Sep. 16th-17th, 2023, for which there was an urgent Call for Astronomers to validate the increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion beginning in these two days and subsequently, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to these two days' JRH time-interval! Data is still missing regarding this urgent call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to validate this year's Sep. 16-17th UNCIARE.) Nevertheless, one of the two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which have been empirically validated as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM is this UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction! As shown above, this "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (JRH) "Critical Prediction" was validated empirically based on the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE) which supports "G-D's Physics" annual increase at the JRH's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) two days' time-interval! Indeed, such a CAGUARE cannot be accounted for GRT's "constant-rate" expansion of the universe due to the (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" concepts – but precisely confirms "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction"! This is because based on "G-D's Physics" CHCF postulate which takes place every consecutive JRH's (two days' time interval and remains constant throughout the whole subsequent

Jewish Year) it is expected that the universe's expansion rate will increase "over time", i.e., leading to the observed CAGUARE's UNCIARE-JRH phenomenon!

b) Earth's CHCF "Functional Center" of the Universe – In "Space" & "Time"!?

Indeed, the existence of "Hubbles Law" (HL), e.g., indicating that the rate of the universe's expansion – relative to "Earth's Functional Epicenter" increases as a function of the distance of any give galaxy from "Earth's Functional Epicenter" points at Earth functioning as the "Universe's Functional Epicenter"! Moreover, when we take into consideration the combination of HL's Earth's Functional Center together with the (abovementioned) CAGUARE UNCIARE-JRH we must reach the inevitable conclusion wherein Earth's CHCF stands at the basis of Earth's Functional Center – i.e., both in "space" and "time"! In other words, the clear empirical evidence positioning Earth as the "Functional Center" of the universe, as evidenced by HL & associated CAGUARE UNCIARE-JRH indicate that Earth's CHCF is responsible for Earth's UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., every consecutive Jewish Year), and when taken together with HL indicate that Earth's CHCF serves as the "Functional Center" of the entire physical universe both in "space" and "time"!

c) The UCP's "Non-Continuous Computation of the Universe" (UCP-NC-CU)!

The next "step" in our new understanding of the fundamental "metamorphosis" that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm creates in our basic understanding of the true "origin", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe is associated with "G-D's Physics" other unique "Critical Prediction" validation, e.g., associated with the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings! According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's computation of the entire physical universe (as well as of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) is "non-continuous", i.e., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frame/s (e.g., therefore the whole physical universe has been redefined as representing only a "computationally-variant" manifestation of the singular "computationally-invariant" UCP which exists "constantly, continuously and uniformly" both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely existing without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!) Indeed, "G-D's Physics" (second) "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings' unique "Critical Prediction" – differentially predicted this "Proton Radius Puzzle" key findings, wherein the relatively "more massive" Muon particle would be computed by the UCP as more "spatially-consistent" than the relatively "less-massive" electron particle (across a series of UF's frame/s)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the UCP's computation of any given particle's "mass" value is based on the UCP's "Object-consistent" computation of each given particle – i.e., with more massive particles being computed as more "spatially-consistent" (as outlined previously) This leads to the UCP's computation of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle as being more "spatially-consistent" than the less-massive electron particle, which then leads to the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings of the relatively "smaller, more accurate measurements" of the Hydrogen's Proton Radius – when encircled by the relatively "more massive" Muon particle, than when encircled by the "standard electron" particle! But, implied within this empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" unique "Proton-Radius Puzzle" "Critical Prediction" is the realization that the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe) – is "non-continuous", i.e., "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, as indicated above, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical inter-

action/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in either the "same"- or "different" UF's frame/s, which also implies that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

As shown above, "G-D's Physics" two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates indicated that the only manner in which the "computationally-variant" universe is "originated", ("dissolved"), "sustained" and "developed" – at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec" is based upon the UCP's THCD's-UCF, which has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards reaching the universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah" State of the universe, in which both Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony"!

Since the UCP's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe relates to Humanity's attainment of such a "Perfected Geulah State", in which all human-beings realize their "oneness" with this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., including their realization of the UCP's basic fundamental "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle": which "teaches" every individual human-being to regard any other human-being as "integral inseparable parts" of this same singular higher-ordered UCP, therefore we see that the UCP's execution of every consecutive UF's exhaustive spatial pixels – strongly relates to its computation of each individual human-being's Moral Choice/s at every "minimal time-point", including the (previously delineated) possibility of "Teshuvah" (e.g., corresponding to the UCP's eighth "Teshuva" HCD, which allows every human-being to carry out a sincere "Teshuvah" remorse and conscious decision to not repeat any specific immoral action); which then alters and changes the UCP's computation of the subsequent (ninth) "UCP's Actual Computed Object", (i.e., in terms of "avoiding" and "altering" that individual human-being's next subsequent UF's frame/s presentation of an "equivalent negative situation" in which that individual human-being would have to experience the same "negative immoral situation" which he/she inflicted pain/suffering upon any other individual human-being – since that individual human-being has carried out a genuine "teshuvah" regarding his/her "immoral choice/s")! So, we can see that at the very center of the UCP's continuous creation- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe's development) stands the UCP's consideration of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – at the JRH's two-days' time-interval, which brings about the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCI-ARE), as well as the UCP's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle which affects that UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in any subsequent UF's frame/s of the universe), and advances the whole of Humanity towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe!

K. Plausibility of "G-D's Physics" New "Universe's Seven Days Origination" (USDO) Model

It is important to note (on a philosophical-scientific level) that since the actual capacity of Science (or Physics) to carry out any direct measurement of the "origination" of the universe – is strictly negated by GRT, due to the fact that we cannot move at a speed exceeding the "Speed of Light" (and therefore cannot "move back in time" to directly observe the actual "origination" of the universe!) therefore, we can only "contrast" between different Scientific Paradigms – such as the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying GRT's "Big-Bang" Model) and the New "G-D's Physics", and consequently decide which of these Scientific Paradigms prevails! Significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm has been proven to be "more valid" than the Old "Materi-

al-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) based on the empirical validation of its two unique "Critical Predictions" – e.g., associated with the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings and the UNCIARE (JRH)! Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model was negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, and therefore its THCD's-UCF theoretical explanation of the continuous "origination", "dissolution" "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe – towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" must be accepted, including its corresponding stipulation of the "seven days creation" of the entirety of the universe (e.g., with all "inanimate" and "animate" forms including human-beings!) Indeed, a further (even more direct) empirical validation (previously called for Astronomers to carry out) that would test for the appearance of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle in a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) in a greater number of UF's than the equivalent (negatively charged) electron particle would directly validate the ongoing continuous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., giving further support for "G-D's Physics" stipulated (novel) "UCP's Severn Day Creation Model" (UCP-SDCM)!

Over and beyond the clear (abovementioned) validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which forces Science to accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-first Century (valid) Scientific Paradigm, there are several further supporting elements taken from "G-D's Physics" "internal-validity" also pointing at the plausibility of its USDO Model of the origination, as part of the basic "Geulah Perfected State Driven Universe" new understanding of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm!

a) It is clear that the universe could not be caused by the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its accelerated rate of expansion could be accounted for by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, nor through Einstein's Equations' three EEE's (as negated by "G-D's Physics" CDP)!

b) Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm (as noted above) due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, we reached the inevitable conclusion that the universe cannot evolve based on any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s), and therefore that the only "viable means" for explaining the origination- sustenance- "dissolution"- re-computation- and development of the entire physical universe (or of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) can only be given based on the analysis of the singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR that is continuously "originating" – "dissolving" "re-creating" and "evolving" every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!")

c) The complete "dependence" – and in fact "inseparability" of the entire physical universe from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is significantly strengthened based on the (abovementioned) profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates – which indicates that there exist only this one singular reality, which is this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, according to these two (profound) theoretical postulates the entire physical universe (and all of

its exhaustive spatial pixels) does not exist "independently" of this singular UCR – but rather merely represents a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular UCR reality!

d) Hence, we realize that the whole existence- (continuous) origination-sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe totally depends upon the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular UCR/UCP, which were discovered as the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's), alongside the UCP THCD's Universal Computational Formula: as noted above (and previously), these UCP's THCD's and (associated) UCF – all point at "G-D's Physics" "Geulah Driven Universe"! In other words, these UCP's THCD's point at the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for advancing the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity and the universe!

e) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" "Reversed Time Geulah Goal" postulate, the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR from its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime" characteristics (e.g., THCD's) specifically leading to the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of "Peace", "Harmony", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's Geulah State and accompanying behavior!)

f) When taken together with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion stipulated to occur during the two days' Jewish "Rosh Hashanah" (New Year) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – which was empirically supported based on the observed (and otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" [CAGUARE]); and more specifically, the current call for Astronomers & Cosmologists to empirically validate a more direct "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE's increased rate of the universe's expansion predicted to take place during the upcoming JRH on Sep. 16th & 17th, 2023 (e.g., relative to prior to Sep 16th-17th , and carry over in an increased universe's accelerated rate of expansion throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year!) These results clearly indicate that the empirically validate CAGUARE (supporting "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction", as explained above and previously) supports "G-D's Physics" centrality of the CHCF as key in explaining the UNCIARE increase in the universe's rate of expansion over the course of the universe's development course (rather than "G-D's Physics" negated purely hypothetical "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" or any of Einstein's other tree EEE's, as described above)!

g) This means that presence of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) must have existed from the initial "origination" of the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! Specifically, when taken together with the UNCIARE-JRH indication that this empirically validated UNCIARE may take place during the JRH's two days' time interval then this implies that from the "first year" of the universe's "origination" by the UCP/UCR, there must have existed this UNCIARE-JRH's CHCF that allowed the (initial) "accelerated expansion rate of the universe! This implies that from the universe's "origination point" by the UCP, shortly after its initial origination, there must have occurred this CHCF JRH UNCIARE phenomenon!

h) When taken together with "G-D's Physics" THCD's UCF (precise) description of the manner in which the UCP accurately computes each subsequent UF's (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{17}$ sec⁻¹") based

primarily upon the UCP's (consecutive) computation of the "seven secondary HCD's" (as "preplanned" and "executed" by the UCP's Three Key Initial HCD's Blueprint Plan for steering the universe from its inanimate through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State") – then this suggests as "plausible" and "reasonable" that the UCP's initial "origination" of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate" state through its pre-planned subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and even perhaps initial recognition by a human-being of the singularity of this UCP, i.e., "G-D" Presence) may have occurred during the first seven days – one day for each of these secondary seven HCD's! Subsequently, after this "first week" in which all "animate" and "animate" (plants, animals and human-beings) have been "originated" by the UCP/UCR, it is suggested that the first CHCF JRH-UNCIARE occurred which allowed for the UCP's first UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

Hence, it's become clear that Science (and Humanity) have now reached a "critical turning point" in its development: instead of Science's "lifelong" basic "Material-Causal" assumption (e.g., including even "Newtonian Classical Mechanics") wherein it was assumed that everything in the universe can be explained as being "caused" by a certain "material-causal" (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any given (finite) number of material elements!?! Such as GRT's basic assumption, wherein the origination of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, or the expansion of the universe is "caused" by the purely hypothetical "Dark Matter" or "Dark-Energy" concepts? Or such as QM's assumed determination of any given subatomic particle or wave entity based on the direct physical interaction/s of a given subatomic "probe" element with a corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function", which "causes" this (assumed) "target's probability wave function" to "collapse" into a single "complimentary" "space-energy" or "mass-time" value?! The New empirically validated "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm completely negated such basic "Material-Causal" assumption – e.g., due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm advanced our new (higher) understanding wherein the only manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) continuously "originates", "sustains", ("dissolves") and "develops" the entire physical universe is based upon its "pre-planned" Blueprint Plan of "steering" the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of the entire physical universe in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP as the sole reality behind the universe (e.g., and also transcending its existence); which will also include Humanity's recognition of this singular higher-ordered UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's "peaceful", "meaningful" and "harmonious" ("goodwill") existence!

The "robustness" of any given Scientific Theory, i.e., and especially the discovery and empirical validation of a New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) in any given discipline – far exceeds its ability (merely) to satisfy the necessary (stringent) criteria to accept this NSP, as more "valid" (and "satisfactory") than the Old Paradigm! As mentioned earlier, according to Thomas Kuhn's (1962) famous (and well-accepted) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", the appearance of a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) ensues the existence of basic fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the "Old Paradigm" – in our case this is the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, characterized by an apparent basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's

inability to account for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, e.g., assumed to be "caused" by (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" which are supposed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which could not be detected or verified experimentally (despite two full decades of trying to do so!)

L. "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's Call for the "Next Eddington's" to Further Validate Its Additional "Critical Predictions"!

Thus, Science has reached a "pivotal turning point", in which the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown to be more valid than the Old "Material-Causal-Random" Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM), based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two (abovementioned unique) "Critical Predictions" pertaining to the UNCIARE (JRH) associated with the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE otherwise "unexplained") phenomenon; and the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM! Moreover, as indicated (above), "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm was also shown capable of resolving the to provide a great advancement of our basic understanding of the physical reality brought about through its (first of its kind) complete unification of the Four basic Physical Features (as well as between the Four fundamental Forces, as shown previously), as well as offer a satisfactory resolution of the (otherwise "unresolved") Gravitational Enigma!

In addition to these major advancements in Twenty-First Century Physics basic understanding of the universe stemming from these growing empirical and theoretical evidences for "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm for 21st Century Physics; "G-D's Physics" is now seeking for the "Next Eddington's" to further validate a few additional (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm that differentiate it from the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's Paradigm's GRT & QM! **Hence Dr. Bentovich is calling leading Theoretical Physicists, Astronomers and Experimental Physicists (all over the world) to collaborate with him in further validating these additional (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" (through his personal e-mail: drbentwich@gmail.com):**

a) UNCIARE-JRH:

It is important to point out another (direct) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in continuation to the already validated UNCIARE unique Critical Prediction: As mentioned above, the UNCIARE Critical Prediction's empirical validation denotes that the universe's rate of expansion has increased from its early stage "Background Radiation" Cosmological measures to the current Astronomical indices of its contemporary rate of expansion! As noted, this result confirms "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE Critical Prediction wherein the universe's accelerated rate of expansion increases over time – in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's assumption wherein the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" is assumed to "cause" a "constant-rate" expansion of the universe (e.g., despite the abovementioned principle negation of the Old "Material-Causal" SRCS/SRNCS "flawed" computational structure which was negated by "G-D's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle", CDP)! Hence, the increase in the universe's rate of expansion over time has already been validated (as the unique UNCIARE Critical Prediction of "G-D's Physics") – but a more specific (direct) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm can be tested based on a specific **"time-sensitive" measurement of the universe's increase in its expansion rate during the two-days' special time-interval of the "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah" (JRH, New Year) which occurred in the previous year on September 16th & 17th (2023) and onwards – relative to the universe's rate of expansion prior to Sep. 16th & 17th (which was expected to be lower than the rate of expansion from Sep. 16th & 17th)!** As noted earlier, this (specific) unique Critical Prediction of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE-JRH's increase in the

universe's rate of expansion, e.g., during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" is hypothesized to be due to "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis", wherein it is assumed that whenever there is a Collective Human Consciousness Focus, e.g., in this case of Millions of Jews all (collectively) focusing on this singular UCP, then this brings about a "Non-Continuous Increase in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (JRH-UNCIARE Critical Prediction)! **Therefore, I am calling all Astronomers and Cosmologists (in the world) to collaborate with me directly (through me email: drbentwich@gmail.com) by carrying out this important further direct empirical validation of the JRH-UNCIARE Critical Prediction – which if validated, will provide yet another (direct) support for "G-D's Physics" New 21st Century Scientific Paradigm!**

c) A "Non-Earth Loci – Asymmetrical Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (NEL-AUARE)!

An additional (even more direct) testing of the Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion would be an empirical validation of a measurement of the universe's "Asymmetrical" measurement of the universe's accelerated rate of expansion s , i.e., an "Asymmetrical" accelerated expansion rate – of the farthest regions of the universe, when measured at a location "distant" from Earth (e.g., such as for instance from "Mars" or other "distant" Non-Earth location)! This is because, if indeed, any such measurement of the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (of a greater rate of expansion proportional to the distance from Earth's measurement) would be found to be "Asymmetrical" (in all directions – for all furthest regions of the universe), as opposed to the accelerated ("symmetrical" or "equivalent") rate of the universe's expansion as measured from "Earth's Universe's Epi-center" (EEU), then this would indicate that indeed Earth's (CHCF) Epicenter is in fact that the (functional) center of the entire physical universe!

d) Greater Number of "Fine Temporal Measurements" (FTM) for (relatively) "More Massive Particles than for (relatively) Less Massive Particles!"

"G-D's Physics" unique "Critical Prediction" predicts a greater number of times that a relatively "more massive" particle (e.g., such as a "Muon") would be detected across a given period of time – relative to the number of times that a "less-massive" particle (such as the 'electron') would be measured during that time; Based on 'G-d's Physics' New Paradigm's computational definitions of "mass" – as the degree of "object-consistent" presentations of a given object (across a given number of Universal Frames, UF's), therefore it follows that a relatively 'more massive' particle ('Muon') would appear across a greater number of consecutive UF's frames than a less massive particle ('electron')! This surprising new "critical prediction" of 'G-d's Physics' Paradigm, wherein the 'more massive' particle would appear across a greater number of consecutive UF's is attributed to the fact that without the availability of (extremely) "Fine Temporal Measurements" (FTM) technological measuring devices, such unique 'critical –prediction' could not be verified! Perhaps equivalent to the empirical validation of Relativity Theory which necessitated very high velocity measurements in order to differentiate it from the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm, so it is suggested that the conductance of such "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) in advanced Subatomic Accelerators would allow Science to validate 'G-d's Physics' New Paradigm's 'critical prediction' regarding the greater number of times that the 'more massive' (Muon) particle would be detected across a given (minimal) period of time, relative to the number of times that the 'less massive' (electron) particle would be detected during the same (minimal) period of time! Obviously, to the extent that this 'critical prediction' would be validated empirically, then this could not be explained by RT or QM (e.g., taking into account any systematic subatomic "measurement biases", as taught by QM).

e) Discovery of "G-D's Physics" New Tentative "Universal Computational Formula - Computational Table" (UCF-CT)!

G-d's Physics": Beyond the "Standard Model" & Discovery of The New

"UCP's THCD-UCF Computational Table"! The manner in which the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm goes beyond the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is based on its novel understanding- and computational definitions- of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time"; As we've seen, based on "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's complete unification of these four basic physical features within the singular "Universal Computational Formula" (e.g., for the first time in Physics!) – e.g., as "secondary computational" properties of the singular higher-ordered UCP's computation of "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time"), our basic understanding of the basic constituents of the physical universe, as well as its basic dynamics (evolution) undergoes a fundamental profound metamorphosis; But, perhaps prior to explicating the precise nature of this fundamental metamorphosis of our basic understanding of the true nature- origin- dynamics- and evolution- of the entire physical universe, which also includes a transcendence of the "Standard Model", lets mention (once again) the two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" profound postulates of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm: Essentially, these two profound theoretical postulates indicate that since only the "Universal Computational/ Consciousness Principle" (UCP) remains constant- continuous and "unaltered"- both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., in which it computes every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe at every such minimal time-point), and also solely remains "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., without the presence of the physical universe); whereas the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) exists only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as being computed simultaneously by the UCP) but "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; therefore, the "Computational Invariance Principle" reasons that only this "computationally-invariant" UCP may be regarded as "real", "continuous" and "constant", whereas the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) may only be regarded as "computationally-variant", i.e., regarded as only "phenomenal" and "transient"; In fact, according to the second associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) theoretical postulate, since only the singular higher-ordered UCP may be regarded as "real", "constant" and "uniform", whereas the entire physical (e.g., including its four basic physical features pertaining to all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) represents only a "transient" and "phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCR, therefore the UCR theoretical postulate asserts that there exists only one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" – which manifests as the physical universe "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, and remains solely (without the presence of the physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's! Indeed, the discovery of this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) signifies a major "Paradigmatic-Shift" – not only from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of 20th century's RT & QM) to the New "A-Causal Computation" "G-d's Physics" Paradigm, but also "philosophically"; It alters our basic appreciation and understanding of the physical universe, i.e., in terms of its origin- dynamics- evolution- (and even "Ultimate Goal" of the universe!) If the universe does not exist as a "constant", "solid" "material" entity, but is metamorphosed into merely representing a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of the only "real" singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality", then our basic understanding of the origin-dynamics- and evolution- of the entire physical universe is also altered in a very basic and fundamental manner: Based on the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's realization wherein since this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and the entire physical universe also "dissolves" back into the singularity of this UCP/UCR "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; therefore "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm asserts that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interac-

tion/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s! Therefore, the very basis of our Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's understanding of the origin- dynamics- and evolution- of the physical universe are undermined- challenged- and in fact negated! This is simply because if there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in single- or multiple- UF's frame/s), then the universe's assumed origination by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event must be negated and rejected! Likewise, we cannot assume (any longer) that the continuous evolution and accelerated expansion of the universe is "caused" by Einstein's Equations assumed "Material-Causal" relationships between certain "massive-objects" and their "curvature of Space-Time", or conversely that the "travelling-pathways" of these "massive-objects" and other "less-massive objects" is "caused" by this "curvature of Space-Time"! Nor can the accelerated expansion of the universe (any longer) be assumed to be "caused" by the effects of purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts (e.g., assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but yet could not be detected to date even after two full decades of various experiments attempting to do so!) Instead, we reach the inevitable conclusion that the entire physical universe does not exist as a "solid", "constant" "material-entity" – it has not been "created" or "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, because there could not have existed any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, e.g., in the "first", "second", "third" or indeed "nth" UF's frame/s; the entire physical universe is being created "anew" at every consecutive UF's frame/s simultaneously for all of its exhaustive spatial pixels by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR – and in fact only a manifestation of this singular "Universal Consciousness Reality"! The universe is more truly being recognized as a continuous "manifestation" of this singular higher-ordered UCR and as entirely "dependent" upon the continuous "computation"- "dissolution"- "recreation" and "evolution" by this singular higher-ordered UCR! To make this new profound realization of "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" "Universal Consciousness Reality" perhaps even clearer – "imagine" (for a second) what "happens" to the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s: it completely "dissolves" back into the singularity of this UCR! In other words, the entire physical universe "ceases to exist" "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Moreover, the only possibility of the continued "existence" of the entire physical universe (e.g., and of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) – is entirely "dependent" upon the "memory", "re-creation" and "evolution" of every such exhaustive spatial pixel by this singular higher-ordered UCR! So, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire physical universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) – is entirely dependent upon- and in fact is but a manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality"! Hence, whether we examine the universe at the "microscopic" quantum level or "macroscopic" relativistic level, we reach the inevitable conclusion that the universe does not operate based on any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between certain "massive-objects" and their (assumed) "causing" of the "curvature of Space-Time", or based on any (direct or indirect) physical relationships between any subatomic "target's" (assumed "probability wave-function") and corresponding "probe" element – which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse" of the target's "probability wave-function" (into a singular "complimentary" energy-space or mass-time value)! Instead, "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm's discovery of the existence of a singular higher, "Universal Consciousness Reality" – upon which the entire "existence", "dissolution", and "evolution" of the universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) entirely depends alters our basic understanding of the basic nature, dynamics and evolution of the universe; we realize that none of the multifarious "relativistic" or "quantum" elements, forces, or particles etc. exists "continuously" – but only "transiently" and "phenomenally" as a manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCR, which constitutes the only "real" continuous "reality" un-

derlying the entire physical universe! There are two direct theoretical ramifications ensuing from this profound realization of the New (empirically validated) "G-d's Physics" discovery of the existence of this singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR): a). The UCR's "Universal Computational Formula": Negating the "Standard Model's" Material-Causal Assumption! First, this profound realization of "G-d's Physics" singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) constituting the only "real" reality underlying the "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the physical universe – when combined with "G-d's Physics" discovery of the singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe through the UCP's simultaneous integrated computation of the four basic physical features (of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time") for each exhaustive spatial pixel; reveals that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical relationship between any "independent" material entities, e.g., be it relativistic "massive-objects"/"less-massive objects" and their assumed "curvature of Space-Time", or be it any subatomic particles, forces, entities etc.! This is simply because (once again) this UCP's singular "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) – so there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, or between any two (or more) subatomic "particles", "forces" etc. This possesses profound theoretical ramifications – i.e., first and foremost, it negates the basic "Material-Causal" assumption underlying the "Standard Model"! This is because the basic "Material-Causal" assumption underlying the "Standard Model" is that it is based on direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain elementary particles and other particles that Three (out of four) Forces of Nature, i.e., "Weak"/"Strong" Nuclear Force", and "Electromagnetic Force" are being explained (e.g., with the fourth "Gravitational Force" currently not being explained by the "Standard Model"); But, since according to this "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), then there cannot exist any such "material-causal" direct (or even indirect) physical interactions between any two (or more) "elementary particles", "forces" etc.! Therefore, instead of the current "Standard Model", which explains those Three Forces in terms of them arising from an assumed direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between specific "particles" or "forces", the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm suggests that the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s), thereby giving rise to the entire UF's frame and negating the possibility of the existence of any direct or indirect "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such subatomic particles; Interestingly, this New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm has been shown to offer a satisfactory alternative explanation replicating all relativistic and quantum phenomena, laws, and effects based on the discovery of this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR's consecutive computation of an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") Thus, for instance, the New "G-d's Physics" accounted for the apparent "curvature of Space-Time" by certain "massive-objects" alternatively through its conceptualization of the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) based on two (out of three) of its "Computational Dimensions", i.e., of "Framework" ("frame"/"object") and "Consistency" ("consistent"/"inconsistent") giving rise to the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy" (e.g., "Frame"-consistent and "inconsistent" UCP's computation), "mass" and "time" (e.g., "Object"-consistent and "inconsistent" computational measures, respectively); Indeed, the alternative theoretical explanation that "G-d's Physics" offers to what appears to be a (direct) "material-causal" physical relationship between certain "massive-objects" and their "curvature of Space-Time" is based on this UCP's simultaneous computation of "more massive" objects as more "spatially-consistent" (e.g., as defined through the mentioned UCP's "Object-consistent" computational definition), relatively to "less-massive" ob-

jects – which therefore creates "high-mass"/"more spatially-consistent" regions within the series of UF's frames, as opposed to "low-mass"/"less spatially consistent" regions, which therefore seem to "disappear" or be "less spatially-consistent" relative to the "high-mass"/"more spatially-consistent" regions; which therefore gives the "impression" as if the more massive "high-mass"/"more spatially-consistent" "curve Space-Time" – but in truth, it is only the distribution of those "more massive"/"more spatially-consistent" regions which remain relatively constant" across the given series of UF's frames, as opposed to the distribution of the other "less-massive"/"less spatially-consistent" regions around the (former) "more massive"/"more spatially-consistent", which gives the "appearance" of the "curvature of Space-Time" by certain "massive objects"! Somewhat similarly, the profound new explanation of "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Paradigm for the Four basic Forces of Nature – which for the first time in Physics successfully unifies between all of them, e.g., and not just between Three of them as explained in the "Standard Model"; and perhaps even more significantly, also unifies for the first time in Physics (history) between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – going beyond Einstein's General Relativity Theory's capacity to unify between "space" and "time" (as the four dimensional "Space-Time" continuum), between "energy" and "mass" (as the " $E=Mc^2$ " Energy-Mass Equivalence), and connect "mass" with "Space-Time" as "curving Space-Time"; the new "G-d's Physics" explanation for the complete unification of those Four Forces as well as of the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") is based on the abovementioned novel "Universal Computational Formula" indicating the UCP's simultaneous computation of those four basic physical features for every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) based on the UCP's new computational definitions derived from the UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computations! In this manner, the novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) offers an entirely new (and profound) understanding of the "composition", "true nature", and "dynamics" of the entire physical universe! This is because through its realization that the UCP necessarily has to compute (simultaneously) the four basic physical features for each exhaustive spatial pixel - since they represent "integrative-complimentary" facets of the UCP singular computation of the degree of "consistency" or "inconsistency", e.g., pertaining to any exhaustive spatial pixel relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "internal composition" of any such given spatial pixel ("object") we realize that what seemed to be those four basic "independent" physical features, e.g., of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" are in truth but different "complimentary-integrative" computational by-products of the same singular higher-ordered UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixels' "frame"/"object" – "consistent"/"inconsistent"! In this manner, "G-d's Physics" new "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) was shown capable of unifying the four basic physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") as "complimentary-integrative" computational facets of the same singular higher-ordered UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)! Likewise, it was shown that the Four basic Forces of Nature ("Weak"/"Strong Nuclear" forces, "Electromagnetic" and "Gravitational" Forces) can also be derived from this singular UCP's "Universal Computational Formula" based on the recognition that the three "Energy-related" Forces mentioned, i.e., "Weak"/"Strong Nuclear" and "Electromagnetic" Forces are computed by the singular UCP as different "frame"-inconsistent energy computations, whereas the Fourth "Gravitational Force" is computed by the UCP as "object-consistent" "mass-related" computation, as explained above and previously; But since all these Four Forces are derived from the same singular UCP's UCF through the UCP's computation of "frame"-consistent ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") integrative-complimentary computations, they are all integrated as part of the UCP's singular computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)! In this manner, it is

understood that there cannot exist any "independent" physical features, or "independent" Forces" or "independent" relativistic and quantum elements because all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe are computed simultaneously by this singular higher-ordered UCP in terms of their "frame"/"object" – "consistent"/"inconsistent" computations! Indeed, this singular UCP's UCF has been also shown to completely integrate all quantum and relativistic features as integral elements within the same singular higher-ordered UCP's computation, as can be glanced from the two respective "Relativistic/ Quantum Formats" of the UCP: This UCF embeds key Relativistic and Quantum relationships (and laws) within this singular (novel) UCF (e.g., The Relativistic "Energy-Mass Equivalence", and Quantum "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's Complimentary Pairs") as can be seen from the UCF's two (respective) Relativistic and Quantum Formats: UCF's Relativistic Format: $e \times s/t = m \times (c^2/h)$ UCF's Quantum Format: $t \times m \times (c^2/h) = s \times e$ We therefore realize that the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm metamorphosizes our basic understanding of the basic nature and dynamics of both the relativistic and quantum realms; wherein it is understood that there cannot exist any direct (or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s, e.g., at either the quantum or relativistic levels, but rather that the UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This also implies that the basic "material-causal" assumption standing at the basis of the "Standard Model" has to be challenged and negated: The subatomic realm does not operate based on the existence of "independent-particles" which interact with each other, thereby producing certain quantum phenomena, as well as giving rise to the Three Forces (abovementioned)! This is because as stipulated (above and previously), there cannot exist any such "material-causal" direct or indirect physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in any single or multiple UF's frames – e.g., due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's. Moreover, we've already seen that in the even the existence of "independent" or "separate" relativistic or "quantum" elements is negated based on the New "G-d's Physics" UCF, since it points at the simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein replacing the "Standard Model" is "G-d's Physics" New (profound) understanding that the universe does not operate through- or is not based upon- the existence of any "subatomic particles" – but is rather permeated and continuously being created- "dissolved"- recreated- and evolved- solely through the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe at every minimal "time-point" (e.g., producing the extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" at the unfathomable rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ "!) b). The "UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula": Indeed, this new profound realization of the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm wherein the universe does not exist as a "solid-material" entity, nor does it operate based on any direct- or indirect- "material-causal" physical interactions between any number of "subatomic-particles" (as assumed by the "Standard Model"), nor are the Four basic Forces underlie by such direct or indirect "material-causal" interactions between such "elementary particles"(!); but is rather solely explained through the UCP's singular higher-ordered continuous (simultaneous) computation- "dissolution"- recreation- and evolution- of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the physical universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹"); inevitably led to the discovery of the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD-UCF) "expanded" format of the abovementioned UCF! As explicated and delineated previously: c). "G-d's Physics" Novel "Computational Table"! We now reach the culmination of "G-d's Physics" complete new description of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP

simultaneously computes the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal time point's" extremely rapid series of UF's (e.g., " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹!) This new profound understanding and description of the physical universe comprises an understanding that one the once hand, due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s, there cannot exist any "material-causal" (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any number of subatomic particles at any single or multiple UF's frame/s – thereby negating the Standard Model's basic underlying "Material-Causal" assumption; but, on the other hand, precisely due to the "mechanics" of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising each such consecutive UF's frame/s through the (abovementioned) "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD-UCF) it is understood that the "apparent composition" of the entire physical universe by "elementary particles" must conform to- and be "comprised of"- this THCD-UCF computational definition and properties! In other words, even though the entire physical universe cannot include any direct or indirect "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – hence cannot operate through any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any number of "elementary particles"; nevertheless, the UCP's continuous computation- "dissolution"- re-creation- and evolution- of all such "elementary particles" is strictly based on this novel ("expanded") THCD-UCF computational definitions, and accompanying (previously delineated) computational definitions of the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features (for each exhaustive spatial pixel simultaneously for every consecutive UF's frame/s!):

We therefore inevitably reach the discovery of the novel "UCP's THCD-UCF's Computational Table"! which for the first time in Physics unifies all apparently "elementary particles" based on their mutual (necessary) computation by the singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., based on the THCD-UCF! Essentially, this THCD-UCF formulates (and constrains) the possible computational relationships between the four basic physical features of every subatomic particle, which therefore predicts- and explains- every existent- as well as every prospective- subatomic particle, thereby giving rise to the novel "UCP's THCD-UCF Computational Table"; **Specifically, it is predicted that every existent (e.g., discovered) or prospective (e.g., to be discovered) subatomic particle would conform to the UCF's stipulated computational relationships between the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – alongside the above outlined computational definitions of each of these four physical features!**

Thus, the discovery (and empirical validation) of "G-D's Physics" New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm – not only unifies between the Four basic Physical Features of "space", "time", "energy" and "mass" (for the first time in Physics: since Einstein's General Relativity Theory was only capable of unifying between the "pairs" of "Space-Time", and the well-known "Energy-Mass Equivalence", and the curvature of Spacetime by certain "massive objects" etc., but could not completely unify between these Four Physical Features); but even more significantly points at the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which constitutes the only "computationally-invariant" Reality that exists both "during" the UCP's computation of every consecutive UF's frame's (array of exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features), and also solely exists without the presence of any physical universe (e.g., including all of these exhaustive spatial pixels for each such consecutive UF's frame/s) "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!

This constitutes a profound metamorphosis of Physics' (and more generally, Science's) basic understanding (and appreciation) of the "true nature" of the entire physical universe – being "comprised" of this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which exists both

"during" its computation of each consecutive UF's frame/s and "manifests" as the whole physical universe, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! This means that according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) UCR – which manifests as the physical universe, i.e., computing every exhaustive spatial pixel's four (basic) physical features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" in the universe, at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s; and solely existing (e.g., without the presence of any physical universe!?) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

In fact, the capacity of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm (e.g., empirically proven to be more valid than the Old "Material-Causal Random" Paradigm of Twentieth century's GRT & QM) to completely unify between the Four (basic) Physical Features (of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time") was based on its profound discovery of the UCP's three "Computational Dimensions" – and specifically of two of these "Computational Dimension", i.e., "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency"(consistent/inconsistent) whose four possible combinations yield those Four basic Physical Features! Hence (as shown and delineated previously), the UCP's complete unification of these Four basic Physical Features is based upon a profound realization that each of these Physical Features represents a specific UCP's: "Frame"- "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object"- "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computation:

The UCP's Computational Definitions of the Four Physical Features:

We thus begin realizing that even through these Four Physical Features seem like "independent" physical entities, they (in fact) only represent different computational facets of the same singular UCP's (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (e.g., for every consecutive UF's frame/s)!

Moreover, these Four basic Physical Features have been shown to be completely integrated (and unified) within the UCP's single "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF):

UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA

This means that in reality – not only **those Four (basic) Physical Features do not exist "independently" of the UCP!?** (because they are computed simultaneously by the same singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., through the singular UCF Formula); but more profoundly, these Four Physical Features do not exist "continuously" "consistently" or "invariantly" – "in-between" any two consecutive UF's Frame/s (because they simply "dissolve" back into the singularity of the UCP during these times)!? **Even "during" each such consecutive UF's frame/s each of these Four basic Physical Features** (in which each of these Four Physical Features is computed by the UCP simultaneously for every exhaustive spatial pixel/s comprising the entire physical universe) – **they exist only as "computed" ("sustained" and "evolved") by this singular higher-ordered UCP** (and "exists" only for a "trillionth-trillionth- etc. of a sec": " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ")! In other words, we start realizing that the entire physical universe only exists as a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of this singular UCP or UCR!

There only truly exist one singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists "uniformly", "consistently" and "continuously" (e.g. "computationally-invariantly") – both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (simultaneous exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe!); and also exists "solely" without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! **In other words, we begin realizing that the entire physical universe does not exist as an "independent material reality", but (in fact) only represents a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of this singular UCR Reality!**

This profound new realization of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is especially profound (and exciting) since it is also associated with "G-D's Physics" **explication of this singular higher-ordered UCR's/UCP's "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – and it's constant ("incessant") striving to "steer" the world towards its "Perfected Geulah State"!** As delineated (previously), we obtain an entirely different (and exciting) new "picture" of the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP computes every consecutive UF's Frame/s (exhaustive spatial pixels!) Four basic Physical Features based on an elaborated "UCP's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula"! (THCD's -UCF).

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

Diagram 1: UCR's Complete GDD, CMD, DEMP, Gim. THCD's

M. A New Singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" – Geulah Driven Universe!

Thus, we reach an entirely new (profound and exciting) understanding of the true nature and even "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of the entire physical universe! No longer can we view the physical universe through the "glasses" of the Old "Material-Causal Random" Paradigm of Twentieth Century's GRT or QM! We cannot (any longer) assume that the universe was created by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event (e.g., "accidentally")! This is because (as delineated and explained thoroughly previously), there could not have existed any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s (e.g., including the negation of any such interaction between such as assumed initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event and the creation of any suns galaxies, energy or mass- in the "first", "second"... trillionth" etc. UF's frame/s!?) Likewise, we cannot assume as does GRT that the universe evolves based on direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between certain "massive-objects", and their "causing" of the "curvature of Space-Time" (or conversely, the determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive objects" or of other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by their direct or indirect "material-causal" physical interaction/s with the assumed "curved Space-Time") – once again, because there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s; due to the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of all of the universe's exhaustive spatial pixels "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s bac into the singularity of the UCP)!

In fact, we realize that all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – merely represent a "transient-phenomenal manifestation" of this singular higher-ordered UCR, which constitutes the only true and single reality underlying (and indeed transcending) the entire physical universe! Moreover, according to "G-D's Physics" abovementioned THCD-UCF it seems that the entire development of the whole physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular UCP/UCR to reach the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" of the universe (and of Humanity)! According to this new (and profound) realization brought about by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, this singular UCR/UCP Reality has "preplanned" the whole development of the universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate": "plants", "animals", and "human-beings" to reach this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity (Science) and the universe, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime characteristics" (of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!)

In fact, with the current empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two unique (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old MCR's GRT and QM, **we now stand at a most significant "turning-point", not only for Twenty-First Century Physics (e.g., as it "crowns" and accepts "G-D's Physics" as the New satisfactory Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century Physics (and Science, more generally); but even more significantly for the whole of Humanity!** This is because with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for Twenty-First Century – Humanity (and Science) "enter" the beginning of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This implies that with the (inevitable) acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New (valid) Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm, **Science allows Humanity to enter and begin the fulfillment of the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected" State, in which Humanity begins recognizing the singularity of this UCP/UCR, alongside adopting a life (and existence) that is compatible with the discovery of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) together with its "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!**

Thus, for instance (as shown extensively previously), Humanity's recognition of the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP), which teaches Humanity that this singular UCP/UCR selects one of "multiple possible future/s" – based upon each Individual human-being's moral/immoral choice/s (at every point in time), in order to "balance" (e.g., correct any immoral action/s) and "enhance" every human being's moral behavior! This implies that whenever any individual human-being ("G-d" forbid) opts to inflict pain or suffering upon another individual human-being, the UCP will select for that "offending" human-being one of "multiple possible futures", in which he/she will also have to experience the same degree of pain or suffering in order to reach a sincere state of "Teshuvah" (e.g., sincere sense of remorse and a resolute conscious decision not to repeat any such immoral action, and also trying to rectify and correct that immoral behavior towards that specific "injured" human-being...) In this manner, the UCP's utilization of this DEMP (which comprises one of its THCD's!) advances each and every Individual human-being (as well as Humanity in general!) towards the fulfillment of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity! **We are therefore entering a unique (and "sublime") new phase in the development of Humanity (and fulfillment of the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah Goal State") in which there will be no more wars, violence, aggression etc. – on the contrary, there will prevail a sense of "Goodwill", "collaboration", "assistance" and "harmony" amongst all of Humanity, which will realize our "Oneness" with this singular "All-Goodness", "Moral", "Peaceful" and "Harmonious" UCR (alongside a deepening investigation of the true nature and characteristics of this "sublime" singular UCR)!**

Intriguingly, "G-D's Physics" pointing at Humanity's (current) entering of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" is extremely reminiscent of the Isaiah's (well-known) Prophecy: And they shall beat their swords into plowshares, and their spears into pruning hooks; nation shall not lift up sword against nation, neither shall they learn war anymore... (Isaiah 2:4) And the Great Maimonides' prophecy regarding "That time (of Geulah) there will be no hunger or war, jealousy or competition... and the whole World's preoccupation will be only to know "G-D"! (Hilchut Melachim, 12:3-5)

Dedication

This article is dedicated to my dear beloved wife Shulamit Bentovish (on this special day, 17th of Adar, (ד'תשפ"ד) for her unwavering support of this (extremely important) scientific work, bound to bring about the fulfillment of that "Ultimate Geulah Goal State" of Humanity and the Universe! It is also dedicated with great love to my dear beloved (diseased) Mother, Dr. Tirzah Bentwich whose unbound love and faith in me have allowed to discover this (beautiful and profound) "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm...

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